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**Neural network and data-driven
correction methods for improving the
simulation of alpine snowpack**

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Abstract

This study investigates on the internal structure of snowpack, metamorphism, and their evolution during the winter season using numerical models. A customized snowpack forecast model is used for this scope, enabling to compare simulation's results obtained with different initialization choices and to evaluate methods for improving the accuracy of the snowpack simulation. Specifically, meteorological data from automatic weather stations (AWS), reanalysis and outputs from numerical weather models (NWMs) are respectively used to simulate snowpack characteristics as an input to the SNOWPACK model, a one-dimensional finite element model developed for avalanche forecasting and snow behavior studies. The model is validated using a specially built statistical verification method to assess its performance. In particular, it is evaluated how various meteorological inputs influence snowpack simulations and to identify the best dataset for accurate snowpack representation. Special emphasis is placed on bias correction techniques and the integration of neural networks to enhance model performance. Results indicate that neural network approaches, better than bias-corrected meteorological data, offer improved predictions of snow height and internal snow structure when compared to traditional NWM data.

The promising results of this study support new and encouraging possibilities for understanding the processes related to the snow and improving their predictability over the winter season. Although applied to a specific case study, both bias correction and neural networks methods are general enough to be applied to other location of interest for the snow science. Nonetheless, great improvements in the accuracy of both the snowpack internal structure and the snow quantity are produced by these methods. A similar approach can be used over forecast data to improve the simulations of the snowpack conditions to come. The study's findings are applicable to hydrology, energy production, and avalanche risk management, with significant implications for water resource management in snow-dependent regions.

Abstract

Questo studio indaga la struttura interna del manto nevoso, il metamorfismo e la loro evoluzione durante la stagione invernale utilizzando modelli numerici. A questo scopo viene utilizzato un modello di previsione del manto nevoso personalizzato, che consente di confrontare i risultati della simulazione ottenuti con diverse scelte di inizializzazione e di valutare i metodi per migliorare l'accuratezza della simulazione del manto nevoso. In particolare, i dati meteorologici provenienti da una stazione meteorologica automatica (AWS), le rianalisi e gli output dei modelli meteorologici numerici (NWM) sono utilizzati per simulare le caratteristiche del manto nevoso come input del modello SNOWPACK, un modello monodimensionale a elementi finiti sviluppato per la previsione delle valanghe e gli studi sul comportamento della neve. Il modello viene validato utilizzando un metodo di verifica statistica appositamente costruito per valutarne le prestazioni. In particolare, si valuta come i vari input meteorologici influenzino le simulazioni del manto nevoso e si identifica il miglior set di dati per una rappresentazione accurata del manto nevoso. Particolare enfasi è posta sulle tecniche di correzione dei bias e sull'integrazione delle reti neurali per migliorare le prestazioni del modello. I risultati indicano che gli approcci basati sulle reti neurali, meglio dei dati meteorologici corretti da bias, offrono previsioni migliori dell'altezza della neve e della struttura interna della neve rispetto ai dati da NWM tradizionali.

I promettenti risultati di questo studio supportano nuove e incoraggianti possibilità di comprensione dei processi legati alla neve e di miglioramento della loro prevedibilità durante la stagione invernale. Sebbene siano stati applicati a un caso di studio specifico, sia la correzione dei bias che i metodi delle reti neurali sono abbastanza generali da poter essere applicati ad altre località di interesse. Inoltre, questi metodi consentono di migliorare notevolmente l'accuratezza della struttura interna del manto nevoso e della quantità di neve. Un approccio simile può essere utilizzato sui dati di previsione per migliorare le simulazioni delle condizioni future del manto nevoso. I risultati dello studio sono applicabili all'idrologia, alla produzione di energia e alla gestione del rischio valanghe, con implicazioni significative per la gestione delle risorse idriche nelle regioni dipendenti dalla neve.

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Introduction

Snow is a critical component of Earth's cryosphere, covering approximately one-third of the land surface during peak winter seasons. Its role extends far beyond merely being a seasonal phenomenon. Snow significantly influences global climate patterns, local hydrological cycles, and ecological systems. It acts as a natural insulator, reflecting solar radiation due to its high albedo, and plays a pivotal role in water storage, especially in mountainous and polar regions. Moreover, snow's complex microstructure, including its metamorphosis from one grain type to another, presents challenges in accurately modeling its behavior over time and space. Snow is highly sensitive to external meteorological conditions, and understanding its evolution is crucial for forecasting natural hazards, particularly avalanches, which are a major threat in alpine and other snow-covered regions.

In recent years, there has been a growing need to improve the precision of snowpack simulations, particularly by incorporating higher spatial resolution data from numerical weather models (NWMs). These weather models are essential for initializing snow model simulations, providing vital meteorological inputs such as temperature, precipitation, and wind speed. However, traditional NWMs often lack the spatial resolution necessary to capture the heterogeneity of the terrain and snow behavior in complex environments like mountains. This can limit the accuracy of snowpack models that depend on these inputs, especially for forecasting snow water equivalent (SWE), snowmelt timing, and avalanche risks. High-resolution NWMs are thus crucial to enhance the predictive capabilities of snow models, but achieving this poses several challenges, including the complex interplay of meteorological factors and the significant computational power required for detailed simulations.

The precision of snow models, especially at high spatial resolutions, is vital for numerous applications. One of the primary motivations is the mitigation of avalanche risks, which require accurate predictions of snow layer stability and changes within the snowpack. Avalanche forecasting relies heavily on understanding the stratigraphy of snow layers, their cohesion, and their response to changes in temperature and moisture. In addition, improving snow model precision has significant implications for hydrology. Snowpacks serve as natural reservoirs, and their meltwater feeds into rivers and groundwater systems during warmer months. Inaccurate models could lead to mismanagement of water

resources, either through premature release of stored water or misjudging the amount of available water later in the season. Traditional numerical weather models (NWMs), while useful for large-scale forecasts, often lack the granularity required for point-specific snowpack predictions. High-resolution models that incorporate the latest techniques in meteorology, machine learning, and snow physics could address these challenges.

The primary aim of this thesis is to improve the precision of snowpack simulations by incorporating high-resolution input from numerical weather models. Focusing on alpine regions, where terrain and meteorological variability make accurate predictions challenging, this study integrates high-resolution NWM data with advanced snow modeling techniques. The objective is to enhance the snow model's ability to predict snow height, snowmelt, and internal snow structure with greater accuracy. Specifically, the study explores the limitations of traditional snow models initialized with low-resolution NWM data, and investigates how improved spatiality in meteorological inputs can enhance snow model performance. The approach particularly focuses on bias correction and data-driven methods such as neural networks. These are intended to adjust the meteorological data point-to-point to start the snowpack simulations, which in turn will provide better insights into snow behavior, including snow height and internal structure.

The first chapter provides an overview of snow, its internal structure, and the metamorphic processes that affect snow grains over time. Both dry and wet metamorphisms are discussed, highlighting their impact on the stability and physical properties of the snowpack. Chapter two outlines the data sources and methods used in the study, including meteorological data from AWS and NWMs. A major focus is on validating the snow model, ensuring alignment between model outputs and AWS observations. The chapter covers snowpack simulation techniques, microphysical processes driving snow changes, and parameterization methods. It also explains bias correction techniques that address systematic errors in the input data and describes the two neural network models used for point-to-point adjustment. Chapter three presents the validation of raw NWM data and reanalysis against AWS measurements, followed by the results of snowpack simulations based on these inputs. The chapter emphasizes the improvements brought by bias correction in both meteorological data and overall snow model accuracy. Chapter four delves into the application of neural networks (NNs) for enhancing snow model accuracy. By leveraging NNs' ability to model complex, non-linear relationships, this chapter shows how machine learning can improve point-to-point precision. The NN-based approach is compared to traditional methods, demonstrating improvements in snowpack predictions. The thesis concludes by discussing the implications of these findings for avalanche forecasting and hydrological applications, and suggests areas for future research and further refinement of high-resolution models.

Chapter 1

The snow

From the time of its deposition until melting or turning from firn to ice, snow on the ground is a fascinating and unique material. Snow is a highly porous, sintered material made up of a continuous ice structure and a continuously connected pore space, forming together the snow microstructure. As the temperature of snow is almost always near to its melting temperature, snow on the ground is in a continuous state of transformation, known as metamorphism. At the melting point, liquid water may partially fill the pore space. In general, therefore, all three phases of water can coexist in snow on the ground.

Snow is a crucial cryospheric component of the climate system. It perennially covers the large continental ice sheets almost entirely and the Earth's sea ice and a large fraction of terrestrial areas without ice in the northern hemisphere seasonally. Due to its particular physical properties, snow plays multiple roles in the Earth system. Its high albedo gives rise to the positive snow albedo feedback [1] [2]. Snow, typically, has a higher albedo than bare ground or vegetation, and the presence of snow can lead to sharp increases in reflected radiation, leading to lower surface temperatures. Through its modulation of surface albedo, snow cover is considered an important feedback within the climate system, especially when amplified by the retreat and advance of boreal vegetation. Feedback works because higher temperatures reduce the snow-covered surface. Eventually, the decreased reflecting surface causes higher radiation absorption, which in turn increases the temperatures. This mechanism amplifies global climate variations and is thought to be a driver of the observed Arctic amplification of current global warming [3], as at higher latitude the cryosphere is more present and changes faster. The same dynamic works with the observed amplification of global warming at high altitudes [4], where also the change of atmospheric quantities, such as humidity, with temperature influences the feedback loop. Similarly, snow acts as a "fast climate switch" on shorter (weekly and seasonal) timescales, with observed strong coupling between temperature and snow cover on regional scales [5]. Insulation of the underlying soil in winter strongly influences the soil temperature regime and thus the thermal state of permafrost and its carbon balance

[6]. By modifying the snow thermal regime, insulation from snow cover can also indirectly affect soil hydrology by affecting the relative proportion of ice versus liquid water content in the soil, altering rates of infiltration, drainage, and runoff. Changes in soil temperatures and hydrology can further cascade to influence ecological processes, particularly at high latitudes where there is concern about land surface and carbon cycle feedbacks to climate change. These include changes in soil microbial activity, plant nutrient availability, and vegetation. In addition, snow influences the ecosystem carbon balance by protecting low vegetation in winter from frost damage and by conditioning the springtime onset of the growing season[7]. Furthermore, substantial impacts of the presence of snow cover on the atmospheric circulation have been found [5]; in general, the coupling between snow and atmosphere is strongest during the melting season, and the effect of snow was found to last well into the snow-free season because of its delayed effect on soil humidity [8]. Linked to its effect on soil humidity, snow has an obvious and profound impact on water availability in snow-dominated regions[9], and large potential economic impacts of snowpack decrease in a warming climate can be expected regionally[10]. Snow plays a crucial role in the Earth's hydrological cycle, serving as a natural reservoir that stores water during the colder months and releases it gradually as it melts[11]. This process is essential for maintaining water availability, particularly in regions that depend on seasonal snowmelt for their water supply[12]. Furthermore, snowmelt is a key driver of hydropower generation, providing a reliable and renewable source of energy[13]. The importance of snow in these contexts cannot be overstated, as it underpins both water security and energy production for millions of people around the world.

Snow functions as a natural water reservoir by accumulating in large quantities during the winter months and storing moisture in solid state. As temperatures rise in the spring and summer, this snow gradually melts, releasing water into rivers, lakes, and groundwater systems. This slow release is critical for maintaining a steady supply of water during the drier months when precipitation is often lower [9]. In many regions, particularly in mountainous areas, snowmelt is the primary source of water for agriculture, drinking water, and industrial use. For example, the Alps provide vital water resources for much of Europe, feeding major rivers such as the Rhine, Rhône, and Danube. The timing and volume of snowmelt are crucial for water management. A well-distributed snowmelt ensures that water is available throughout the year, preventing shortages during dry periods. However, changes in snowfall patterns due to climate change can disrupt this balance, leading to either too much or too little water being available at critical times.

Snowmelt is also a vital component of hydropower generation, one of the most important sources of renewable energy [13]. Hydropower plants rely on the flow of water to generate electricity, and in many regions, this flow is significantly influenced by the seasonal melting of snow. During the spring

and summer, when snowmelt is at its peak, rivers and streams experience higher water levels, increasing the flow rate into hydropower reservoirs. This enhanced flow enables hydropower plants to generate more electricity, meeting the increased energy demand during these warmer months. In regions where snowmelt is a significant contributor to river flow, such as the Himalayas, the Andes, and the Alps, hydropower is a major source of energy. For example, in Norway, which relies heavily on hydropower for its electricity, snowmelt from the country's mountainous terrain provides a steady and predictable water supply that drives its extensive network of hydropower plants. The reliability of snowmelt as a water source for hydropower is crucial for energy security. Unlike other forms of renewable energy, such as solar or wind, which can be intermittent, hydropower offers a consistent and controllable energy output. However, this reliability is increasingly under threat as climate change alters snowfall patterns, leading to reduced snowpack and earlier melting [11]. This can result in lower water availability during the critical summer months when demand for electricity is high. Protecting and managing snow resources is therefore essential for ensuring the sustainability of these critical systems in the face of a changing climate.

Snow is not just a natural phenomenon; it is the lifeblood of snow sports worldwide. From the powdery slopes of ski resorts to the icy tracks of luge and bobsleigh, snow provides the essential surface on which these sports are performed. The quality, quantity, and timing of snowfall are critical factors that determine the success of snow sports, influencing everything from the performance of athletes to the safety and enjoyment of recreational enthusiasts.

Each sport requires optimal performance of specific snow conditions. The quality of snow is directly linked to the safety of snow sports. Different types of snow present varying levels of risk to athletes and participants. Powder snow, for example, is highly sought after for its soft and forgiving nature, which reduces the likelihood of injury in the event of a fall. However, it can also hide underlying hazards such as rocks or ice. For more extreme snow sports, such as ice climbing or backcountry skiing, snow stability becomes a critical concern. The risk of avalanches is ever-present in these environments, and the stability of the snowpack can be influenced by recent snowfall, temperature fluctuations, and wind. Proper knowledge of snow conditions and avalanche risk management is essential for the safety of participants in these high-risk sports. Temperature also plays a crucial role in snow quality and safety. Warmer temperatures can cause snow to become wet and heavy, slowing down skiers and snowboarders, while extremely cold conditions can lead to brittle, icy snow that is difficult to manage.

The importance of snow extends beyond just providing a surface for sports; it is also a barometer for the health of our environment. Snowfall patterns are sensitive indicators of climate change, and the increasing unpredictability of snowfall poses a significant challenge to snow sports. Warmer winters, shorter

snow seasons, and reduced snow cover are becoming more common, threatening the very existence of some snow sports. As natural snowfall becomes less reliable, many ski resorts and snow sports venues have turned to artificial snowmaking to maintain their operations. While artificial snow can help sustain the industry in the short term, it comes with its own set of challenges. The environmental impact of snowmaking, including high water and energy usage, raises concerns about the long-term sustainability of relying on artificial snow.

Owing to the intermittent nature of precipitation, the influence of wind, and the ongoing metamorphism of snow, distinct layers of snow form the snowpack[14]. Snowpack encompasses all the snow that accumulates on the ground for the winter season or longer. Each snowfall contributes an additional layer. Consequently, the snowpack reveals the chronological history of a winter, from the oldest layers at the base to the most recent layers at the surface. Some layers are so distinctive that weeks later they can be traced back to specific weather events, such as a thick melt-freeze crust resulting from a brief warm period. The behavior and characteristics of the snowpack are contingent upon the distinct layers and their properties. For instance, weak layers, such as those formed by snow-covered surface hoar, can exacerbate the risk of avalanches.

1.1 The internal structure of the snowpack

Each stratigraphic layer differs from adjacent layers above and below by at least one of the following characteristics: microstructure or density, which together define the type of snow; additionally, snow hardness, liquid water content, snow temperature or impurities describe the state of snow[15]. The snow microstructure includes all the characteristics of the porous medium, such as the grain size and shape, the coordination number (intended as the number of bonds that each grain forms on average), the specific surface area and the dendricity. Not all these quantities are relevant for the average description of a layer and often a bulk property that depends on them is used. The bulk properties are all those that describe the snow at an overall level, such as density, temperature, hardness, liquid water content and the snow water equivalent. Most of these are directly linked to the microstructure of the single grains. Thus, at any one time, the type and state of the snow that forms a layer have to be defined because its physical and mechanical properties depend on them[16]. Now, a brief description of the characteristics of the snow is presented. Please note that some of these properties are of the bulk, and some others refer to the microstructure of the snow.

1.1.1 Grain type

The international classification for snow on the ground [14] organizes snow grain types (also known as grain shapes) into main grain type classes (Tab

1.1), which can in turn be broken down into more nuanced sub-classes. The following grain types are typical in avalanche forecasting contexts:

- PP: precipitation particles
These are grains that have just been deposited and did not undergo mechanical or physical modifications. The precipitation particles can have different shapes and dimensions depending on the temperature and humidity of the air during the formation of the crystals.
- DF: decomposing and fragmented particles
Mainly precipitation particles that have been modified by the wind transport or through the snow load. The extent of the decomposition depends on the intensity of the wind action and the duration of the load. Typically, these grains form a resistant layer with high density and hardness.
- RG: rounded grains
The rounding of the grains can happen due to wind action or through thermodynamic processes known as destructive metamorphism. This form of the grains allows the formation of more bonds for grain and thus a compact layer, with high density and hardness.
- FC: faceted crystals (including the subclass rounding facets, FCxr)
These grains are characterized by squared forms and a dimension a little bigger than the rounded grains. They are formed by constructive metamorphism or solid kinetic growth, which makes decrease the bonds between grains and increase the grain size. For this reason, the layers usually are characterized by lower density and hardness.
- SH: surface hoar
These are striated, usually flat crystals, described as feather-shaped. Usually they form on cold snow surface relative to air temperature due to rapid kinetic growth of crystals at the snow surface by rapid transfer of water vapour from the atmosphere toward the snow surface or because the snow surface is cooled to below ambient temperature by radiative cooling. It is fragile and has an extremely low shear strength. The strength may remain low for extended periods when buried in cold dry snow.
- DH: depth hoar
The crystals have the shape of a hollow skeleton usually striated that can be cup-shaped. It forms within the snowpack, in the dry snow because of high temperature gradients. Typically, it is very fragile and low bonded with nearby layers.
- MF: melt forms (including the subclass melt-freeze crusts, MFcr)
These can be individual or clustered rounded crystals held by large ice-to-ice bonds and can be at the surface or within the snowpack. It forms

through the melting of the layer and can also refreeze forming crusts and increasing the strength. If the liquid water content increases and the drainage is blocked, the strength decreases and the density increases.

In general, new snow layers mostly consist of PP and DF; SH and DH are prototypical persistent weak layers, and MFcr layers often promote the faceting of adjacent grains, which weakens the interface. FC, including FCxr, can also be considered persistent weak layers, even though not every faceted layer is a layer of concern according to common snow profile analysis techniques that consider combinations of grain type and grain size (amongst other properties) to identify structural weaknesses in the snowpack.

Class	Symbol	Code
Precipitation Particles	+	PP
Machine Made snow	⊙	MM
Decomposing and Fragmented precipitation particles	\	DF
Rounded Grains	●	RG
Faceted Crystals	□	FC
Depth Hoar	^	DH
Surface Hoar	∨	SH
Melt Forms	○	MF
Ice Formations	■	IF

Table 1.1: Classification of different grain shapes with their symbols and codes (source: [14]).

1.1.2 Grain dimension

Another important characteristic of the snow layers is the dimension of the grains. It is taken as the mean of the crystals' dimensions in a given sample and measured in millimeters; it varies approximately between 0.2 and 5 mm. It depends mainly on the wind that breaks the grains into smaller particles and on the metamorphism after the deposition in the snowpack. The dimension has influence on the density of the layers and on the bonds that connect the grains and thus the hardness.

1.1.3 Hardness

Hardness is the quantity that expresses the resistance to penetration of an object into the snow. It depends on the bonds built between the grains (specified by the coordination number) and their dimension. Measurements can be made with instruments (such as the rammsonde) or through the hand test introduced by De Quervain that uses objects of decreasing areas that can be gently pushed into the snow, thus not exceeding a penetration force of 10–15

N. This test is rather subjective but for every object a corresponding interval of force measured with the rammsonde is given (Tab 1.2).

Term	Hand test			Ram resistance	
	Hand index	Object	Code	Range (N)	Mean (N)
Very soft	1	Fist	F	0–50	20
Soft	2	4 fingers	4F	50–175	100
Medium	3	1 finger	1F	175–390	250
Hard	4	Pencil ¹	P	390–715	500
Very hard	5	Knife blade	K	715–1200	1000
Ice	6	Ice	I	>1200	>1200

¹Here 'pencil' means the tip of a sharpened pencil.

Table 1.2: Table of the hardness classification and the corresponding penetration force (source: [14]).

Snow hardness is a crucial factor in determining the stability of a snowpack, particularly in areas prone to avalanches. Hardness refers to the density and cohesion between layers of snow, influenced by temperature, wind, and snowfall conditions. Softer layers of snow, when situated beneath harder layers, can create weak zones that fail under stress, potentially triggering avalanches [17]. Harder and more cohesive snow layers, especially after being compacted by wind or cold temperatures, tend to stabilize a snowpack by providing a solid foundation. However, abrupt changes in hardness between layers, known as “weak layers,” are a primary cause of slab avalanches [18].

1.1.4 Density

The density of snow can range from approximately 50 kg/m^3 for freshly fallen snow to more than 500 kg/m^3 [14]. Despite being a bulk property, precise measurement of snow density is crucial for microstructure-based studies. Metamorphism typically results in a constant or increasing density. Snow density is vital for determining the snow water equivalent and stability, as it is directly correlated with hardness. The density can be inferred from the grain type and grain dimension to some extent. It is intrinsically related to all other quantities, whether in bulk or in microstructure.

1.1.5 Liquid water content

Liquid water content is defined as the amount of water within the snow that is in the liquid phase. This parameter is synonymous with the free-water content of a snow sample. Liquid water in snow originates from either melt, rain, or a combination of the two. Measurements of liquid water content or wetness are expressed as either a volume or mass fraction; both can be reported as a

percentage (%). Liquid water is only mobile if the residual or irreducible water content is exceeded. The latter is the water that can be held by surface forces against the pull of gravity (capillary action). Residual water content in snow corresponds to a volume fraction of about 3–6 %, depending on the snow type. Liquid water content plays a significant role in snowpack stability, particularly as it influences the mechanical properties of snow. When the liquid water content in the snowpack increases, either due to melt or rainfall, it can significantly reduce snow strength and cohesion between layers [19]. This decrease in strength is critical in avalanche formation, as wetter snowpacks tend to be more prone to failure. As liquid water permeates through the snowpack, it can lubricate weak layers, leading to a reduction in friction and promoting the likelihood of avalanches [20]. However, if the liquid water content remains below the residual water content, the snow retains capillary cohesion, maintaining relative stability. The transition from dry snow to wet snow conditions is one of the key factors avalanche forecasters consider, especially during thawing events or rain-on-snow scenarios.

1.1.6 Temperature

Snow temperature is a key factor in snowpack metamorphism, as it influences both the rate and type of changes occurring within the snow [21]. At higher temperatures, metamorphic processes accelerate, causing snow crystals to change their structure more quickly. The temperature profile of the snowpack, that explains how heat is distributed from surface to depth, is also crucial. This profile helps to determine the temperature gradient that drives the movement of water vapor within the snow [19]. A steep gradient, where surface temperatures are much colder than deeper layers, can lead to the development of weak and unstable layers that are prone to collapse under stress.

Understanding the temperature profile is essential for evaluating snowpack stability [18]. Rapid temperature shifts between layers can indicate areas of vulnerability, where weak layers may form, contributing to the risk of avalanches. Monitoring snow temperature also allows predictions of melt-freeze cycles, which can stabilize or destabilize the snowpack depending on conditions. Thus, snow temperature is critical for assessing snowpack evolution and potential hazards in mountainous areas.

1.2 Metamorphism

Snow metamorphism refers to the change of snow crystals over time [22]. Snow crystals begin to metamorphose from the instant they begin to fall. After new snow is added to the snowpack, the form and size of snow crystals (now labeled snow grains) changes continuously. As snow grains change, layers within the snowpack strengthen and weaken. The variation in snow on the ground arises

not so much from its variable origins as from the fact that snow covers are generally subjected to varying conditions and that snow is a finely dispensed aggregate of ice, water vapor, and water at, or close to, its melting temperature. Accordingly, snow is constantly moving to reduce its surface free energy by densifying and eliminating smaller grains. At the same time it responds to different stimuli produced by its environment, melt water and temperature gradients being the most important.

One type of snow metamorphism is the result of sublimation and deposition. These are physical processes that transform ice to water vapour (without a liquid phase) and vice versa. In the snowpack we see this as ice from grain surfaces transforming into water vapour which is then deposited as ice on other grain surfaces. Sublimation and deposition processes are driven by the temperature gradient of a given snowpack layer. Together, temperature gradient and the movement of water vapour determine whether rounding or faceting processes will dominate within the snowpack. Melt-freeze is another type of metamorphism that changes the composition of snow grains through melting and refreezing, rather than through sublimation and deposition.

The ultimate goal in studying the metamorphism of snow is to understand how the layers in the snowpack change in time and which are the forcing of this change. The comprehension of the phenomena is essential to properly model the changing state of the snowpack. Practically, this inquires the computation of the temperature gradient, that forces the water vapor flux. This calculation cannot disregard the type of the snow of the layers, affecting thermal conduction. The evaluation of the metamorphism is typically performed upon classifying snow into dry and wet, as we describe in the following paragraphs.

1.2.1 Metamorphism of dry snow

Metamorphism in dry snow refers to the transformation processes that snow crystals undergo in response to changes in temperature and pressure, in the absence of liquid water. This process results in the evolution of snow grains, which can either become more rounded or more faceted. The fundamental mechanisms driving these changes are primarily related to water vapor diffusion within the snowpack. To explain this process thoroughly, we need to explore the physics behind the water vapor, particularly diffusion and sublimation.

Snow is a porous material, and its temperature gradient influences water vapor pressure between individual snow grains. Water vapor tends to migrate from areas of higher vapor pressure (warmer regions) to areas of lower vapor pressure (colder regions) (Fig 1.1). This movement is described by Fick's law of diffusion:

$$\vec{J} = -D\nabla C \quad (1.1)$$

where: \vec{J} is the diffusion flux (amount of substance per unit area per unit time), D is the diffusion coefficient, ∇C is the gradient of water vapor concentration.

Figure 1.1: Schematic illustration of the vapor diffusion due to temperature gradient. (source: [14])

The water vapor concentration C (in terms of molecules per unit volume or mass per unit volume) in air is directly linked to the saturation vapor pressure through the ideal gas law. Specifically, the concentration of water vapor is related to the partial pressure of water vapor (which can be the saturation vapor pressure when the air is fully saturated) via:

$$C = \frac{P_v}{R_v T} \quad (1.2)$$

where: P_v is the partial pressure of water vapor (Pa), R_v is the specific gas constant for water vapor ($R_v = 461.5 \text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$) and T is the temperature of the snowpack (K). In the context of snow metamorphism, the saturation vapor pressure over ice $P_{v,s}(T)$ is the maximum vapor pressure that water vapor can exert over an ice surface at a given temperature. When the air is saturated, the water vapor concentration C_s is related to the saturation vapor pressure by:

$$C_s = \frac{P_{v,s}(T)}{R_v T} \quad (1.3)$$

where: $P_{v,s}(T)$ is the saturation vapor pressure over ice at temperature T . Thus, the concentration of water vapor is proportional to the saturation vapor pressure at a given temperature, meaning that, for a given temperature, the higher the saturation vapor pressure, the higher the maximum possible concentration of water vapor in the air. At last, the temperature dependence of the saturation vapor pressure $P_{v,s}(T)$ over ice can be described by the Clausius-

Clapeyron relation, which is an exponential function of temperature:

$$P_{v,s}(T) = P_0 \exp\left(\frac{L_s}{R_v T_0} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right) \quad (1.4)$$

where: P_0 is a reference vapor pressure, L_s is the latent heat of sublimation (2834 kJ/kg for ice) and T_0 is a reference temperature.

In the dry snow, two different process can take place. The key distinction between these two processes lies in the temperature gradient and how vapor pressure differences influence the shape of the snow grains. Rounding is a process of destructive metamorphism, leading to the decay of the original snowflake shapes into more rounded grains, while faceting is a constructive metamorphism, producing angular, sharp-edged crystals due to directional vapor deposition. Therefore, we are mainly interested in the vertical difference in vapor pressure, as this forces the vertical movement of vapor in the snowpack, and the diffusion \vec{J} . The two quantities that mainly influence the vapor pressure are the temperature, as shown in equation 1.4, and the curvature of the surface, as explained by the Kelvin equation 1.5.

Rounding (Destructive Metamorphism) The curvature of a snow grain affects the vapor pressure [21]. This relationship is described by the Kelvin equation:

$$P_v = P_{v,s}(T) \exp\left(\frac{\gamma V_m}{rRT}\right) \quad (1.5)$$

where: P_v is the vapor pressure over a curved surface, γ is the surface tension of ice, V_m is the molar volume of ice, r is the radius of curvature of the snow grain, R is the universal gas constant and T is the temperature. Therefore, the curvature of snow grains affects their vapor pressure. The Kelvin equation demonstrates that sharper (more curved) surfaces sublime faster because the vapor pressure is higher over small radii. This behavior drives the vapor to condense in more concave regions (larger radii), leading to the overall rounding of snow grains.

To further elucidate this, consider the case of two snow grains of radii r_1 and r_2 , where $r_1 < r_2$. From the Kelvin equation, we know that $P_v(r_1) > P_v(r_2)$. Consequently, water vapor will diffuse from the smaller grain (where it sublimates faster) toward the larger grain (where deposition occurs). Over time, this process will reduce the surface area of smaller grains, increasing the size of larger, rounder grains, which contributes to the densification of the snowpack.

So, smaller radii (sharper edges) result in elevated vapor pressures, consequently leading to faster sublimation in these regions. In the presence of a negligible or non-existent temperature gradient within a snowpack, water vapor diffuses randomly among snow grains. This process induces the sublimation of the sharper edges of snowflakes, where vapor pressure is higher due

to curvature effects, and the subsequent deposition of water vapor into concave areas, where vapor pressure is lower. This mass redistribution leads to the smoothing of grains as sharp edges vanish and larger, rounded grains emerge. Over time, this phenomenon increases the density and structural integrity of the snowpack. This process, termed destructive metamorphism, ultimately results in the rounding of snow grains.

Figure 1.2: Graphic summary of the rounding metamorphism. (source: [22])

The rounding process can also be described in terms of the growth rate of the snow grains [23]. The rate of change of the radius r of a snow grain due to vapor diffusion is proportional to the difference in vapor pressure between areas of high and low curvature:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = P_v - P_{v,s}. \quad (1.6)$$

Thus, over time, the size of snow grains increases, leading to a stronger, more cohesive snowpack with rounded grains.

Faceting (Constructive Metamorphism) Conversely, when a substantial temperature gradient exists within the snowpack, water vapor migrates directionally from the warmer regions (lower layers) to the colder regions (upper layers). In such instances, vapor sublimates from the warmer grains and condenses onto the colder grains. This results in the colder grains developing faceted structures, such as depth hoar, due to the preferential deposition on planar surfaces. This phenomenon is known as constructive metamorphism [21].

During faceting, the temperature gradient promotes the formation of angular, faceted crystals instead of rounded grains. The transport of water vapor

Figure 1.3: Graphic summary of the faceting metamorphism. (source: [22])

between grains can be quantified by the vapor diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D\nabla^2 C \quad (1.7)$$

where $\partial C/\partial t$ is the change in concentration of vapor with time, and $\nabla^2 C$ is the Laplacian of vapor concentration, which represents the directional flow of vapor from warmer to colder regions. Faceting typically occurs when the temperature gradient exceeds a critical threshold (approximately 20 K/m). It leads to the growth of angular, faceted crystals as vapor migrates from warmer to colder areas[24]. Faceting weakens the snowpack because angular grains have poor bonding strength, making it prone to avalanche formation.

In the case of faceting, the strong temperature gradient between the snowpack's warmer bottom and colder top results in a directional water vapor flux. This flux can be quantified using the gradient of the vapor pressure:

$$\vec{J} = -D\nabla P_v. \quad (1.8)$$

The vapor pressure P_v at a given location in the snowpack is dependent on the local temperature. A higher temperature gradient causes a higher vapor pressure gradient, driving water vapor from warmer areas (where grains sublimate) to colder areas (where deposition occurs). This directional vapor movement leads to the growth of faceted crystals, which are angular and often have sharp edges.

Faceted crystals form because the rate of deposition on flat surfaces is higher than on curved surfaces, leading to the formation of plates, columns, or depth hoar, depending on the specific conditions within the snowpack [14]. Depth hoar is a classic example of faceted crystals that form in response to a strong temperature gradient, typically found near the base of the snowpack where the temperature contrast is greatest.

1.2.2 Metamorphism of wet snow

Wet snow metamorphism occurs when liquid water is introduced into the snowpack, typically due to surface melting (caused by solar radiation) or rainwater infiltration. This type of metamorphism is often referred to as melt metamorphism, a form of isothermal metamorphism that predominantly takes place when the snow temperature is close to 0°C . In contrast to dry snow metamorphism, which is driven by vapor diffusion, wet snow metamorphism involves the presence of liquid water, which significantly accelerates the metamorphic processes [21].

In melt metamorphism, the key driver is the presence of liquid water. As the temperature rises (typically during the day due to solar radiation or a warm front), snow crystals begin to melt. Liquid water forms in the pore spaces between snow grains, replacing the air and creating a more efficient medium for heat transfer. The process of snow melting and its subsequent transformations can be described as follows [9]:

1. **Melting of snow grains:** When the temperature reaches 0°C , some of the snow crystals begin to melt. The liquid water fills the pores between snow grains, replacing the air pockets.
2. **Rapid heat transfer:** The thermal conductivity of liquid water is significantly higher than that of air. In the snowpack, the heat transfer rate in liquid water is approximately 24 times greater than in air ($\lambda_{water} = 0.58\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$ vs $\lambda_{air} = 0.024\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$). As a result, the presence of liquid water accelerates the metamorphic processes, causing snow grains to melt faster and form larger, more rounded structures.
3. **Grain coarsening:** As snow grains melt, smaller grains or their sharp edges and facets preferentially melt due to their higher surface energy. This process leads to the merging and rounding of snow grains, a process similar to that of dry metamorphism but occurring at a much faster rate. The liquid water acts as a medium through which heat is efficiently transferred, leading to the growth of larger, more spherical grains.
4. **Percolation and capillary action:** The liquid water formed by melting may percolate downward through the snowpack under gravity. However, some water is retained in the pores by capillary action, especially when the pore size is small, such as in fine-grained snow. This retained water enhances the metamorphic processes, facilitating grain growth.

One of the key aspects of wet snow metamorphism is the freeze-melt cycle [18]. As the snow temperature fluctuates around 0°C (e.g., due to diurnal temperature changes, radiative cooling at night, or a sudden drop in air temperature), the liquid water in the snowpack may refreeze. This refreezing creates strong bonds between snow grains, leading to the formation of a dense

and durable layer known as a melt-freeze crust. The process happens when the temperature drops, the liquid water present in the snowpack refreezes. The refreezing process releases latent heat, which slows the cooling rate of the snowpack. As water freezes, it forms thick ice bridges between adjacent snow grains. This process strengthens the mechanical bonds between grains, resulting in a denser and harder snow structure [14]. The frozen liquid water bonds the snow grains together. The new bonds formed are much thicker and stronger than those that form through sublimation processes in dry snow metamorphism. This increases the overall strength and cohesion of the snow layer, reducing the likelihood of avalanche initiation in this layer. Melt-freeze crusts are characterized by their high density, hardness, and strength. These crusts can resist penetration (such as from ski poles or boots) and often have a smooth surface. The strength of a melt-freeze crust can be a stabilizing factor in the snowpack, but if it overlies weaker layers of snow, it can also contribute to the formation of persistent weak layers that pose an avalanche risk. These crusts can create a hard, impermeable barrier that traps water in the layers below, potentially increasing the risk of wet-slab avalanches.

In environments where the snowpack experiences regular diurnal temperature changes, such as in spring or on south-facing slopes, melt-freeze cycles are a common occurrence. During the day, solar radiation causes surface melting, while radiative cooling or air temperature drops at night lead to refreezing. Each successive cycle causes snow grains to grow larger and more rounded, and each refreeze strengthens the snowpack by creating new bonds. These repeated cycles transform the snowpack from one composed of fine grains to a dense, rounded structure. Over time, the snowpack becomes harder, more homogeneous, and less prone to mechanical failure due to the formation of strong bonds between grains.

While melt-freeze crusts are generally strong, wet snow metamorphism can also lead to conditions conducive to wet-snow avalanches [18]. The presence of liquid water can reduce the friction between grains, causing them to slide more easily. If water accumulates in a weaker layer beneath the crust, it can act as a lubricant, increasing the likelihood of a wet slab avalanche. Additionally, the loss of strength due to excessive water content can lead to spontaneous releases of wet loose avalanches.

1.2.3 Sintering

Snow is a viscoelastic material that undergoes large irreversible deformations. The material viscosity, η , relates the stress ρ to the strain rate de/dt , when elastic deformations are small as in the case of snow settling:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = -\sigma_s/\eta_s \quad (1.9)$$

where σ_s is the applied snow pressure (in this case the self-weight of the snow pack) [15]. Therefore, low viscosity values will result in high settlement rates,

while high viscosities will yield low settlement rates. Since the necks are the regions of maximum stress, most of the deformation takes place there. The stresses in the necks may be more than an order of magnitude larger than the stresses in the grains. The necks may be directly compressed and they can also deform in shear. The result is that under compressive loads, the ice grains move closer to each other, the pores occupy a smaller portion of the snow volume and the density increases. The whole process is called pressure sintering and leads to a bond growth which takes place in addition to the kinetic or isothermal bond growth. The calculation of viscosity will be broken into two parts: a nonlinear range and a linear range. This is determined by the properties of ice itself. At low stresses, ice exhibits a nearly linear behavior, and the strain rate ϵ_i is governed by a relation of the form:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_i = \sigma/\eta_i. \quad (1.10)$$

In the nonlinear range, the relationship between stress and strain rate is:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_i = \sigma^n/\eta'_i \quad (1.11)$$

where the exponent, n , may vary between 2.0 and 3.5 and the prime in η'_i points to the fact that the viscosity is different from the one in Eq.1.2.3. The critical stress of 0.4 MPa dividing the linear and nonlinear ranges of material behavior is an ice property[25]. Therefore, whether the behavior of snow is linear or nonlinear is determined by the stress applied to the ice in the necks, not to the snow itself. The constitutive relationship for snow in this program relates volumetric strain rate to hydrostatic pressure. Since this constitutive law is being used in a one-dimensional snow pack model, this is sufficient. This constitutive formulation includes the combined effects of pressure sintering (bond growth), intergranular glide, bond fracture with resultant intergranular slip and elastic response. As such, this formulation is a very comprehensive one in that it includes the important deformation mechanisms, represents the material microstructure and can even calculate evolving anisotropy that results from sustained deformation.

Chapter 2

Data and Methods

2.1 Data

For this work, different data sets have been used. Here a presentation of all of them is done, describing also all the methods to pre-process the data. Most of the data come from the automatic weather station (AWS) called GESS that is described in detail. In addition, the numerical weather models (NWMs) and the reanalysis used for this work are presented and their construction is explained.

2.1.1 Automatic Weather Station

The automatic weather station used for this work is called Gessi (GESS) from the location where it is placed, above Livigno. The AWS is located near the Cantone peak, in a flat area in the northwest slope (N 46.507740, E 10.075780). The station is composed of the following instruments with the listed characteristics. The Campbell Scientific CS215 combined air temperature and relative humidity sensor, installed in 2016 and revised in 2021, comes equipped with natural ventilation protection. The temperature sensor is a precision linear thermistor that operates within a measurement range of -30°C to $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$, offering an accuracy of $\pm 0.15^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a resolution better than 0.1°C . The temperature output is based on resistance variation.

The hygrometer component utilizes a hygroscopic polymer sensor, working on the principle of electrical capacitance variation. It can measure relative humidity within a range of 0 to 100%, with a resolution better than 1%. The hygrometer has a stability of 1% over 12 months and its accuracy is $\pm 2\%$ at 10% relative humidity and $\pm 3\%$ at 90%.

The Campbell Scientific SR50 ultrasonic snow sensor is used to measure snow depth at ground level and includes air temperature compensation. It features an analog interface output for snow level and a digital RS232 interface for snow level and air temperature. It measures snow depths from 0.00 to 8.00 meters, offering a resolution of 1 mm for digital output and 0.5 cm for

Figure 2.1: The location of GESS AWS, source: [26].

analog output. The beam angle is approximately 12° , and it functions within a temperature range of -40°C to $+60^\circ\text{C}$. The sensor is protected by an IP66-rated enclosure and has integrated lightning protection with a discharge capacity of 0.6 kA.

The MTX FAR410BA atmospheric pressure sensor, a piezo-resistive type, operates on the principle of resistance variation to measure atmospheric pressure. It provides an accuracy of ± 0.5 hPa at 22°C , with a measurement range of 850 to 1050 hPa and a maximum limit of 1150 hPa. Its thermal coefficient is 0.06 hPa per degree Celsius. It is equipped with fast Zener protection and operates in temperatures between -30°C and $+60^\circ\text{C}$, housed in a data logger box.

The MTX FAR060AC thermistor sensors are precision linear thermistors housed in stainless steel watertight probes, used for measuring the internal temperature of the snowpack. These sensors provide an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and a resolution of 0.1°C , operating within a temperature range of -30°C to $+50^\circ\text{C}$. The output is resistive for each sensing element, with one common output and six thermistor wires. The sensors are positioned at different heights above the ground surface: +5 cm, +10 cm, +50 cm, +100 cm, and +200 cm.

The Sommer infrared sensor is used for measuring the surface temperature of the snowpack. It provides a resolution of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and the measurement range is from -30°C to $+30^\circ\text{C}$.

The Young Alpine heavy-duty mechanical wind speed sensor without a heater measures wind speed with an accuracy of ± 0.5 m/s up to 5 m/s

Figure 2.2: Picture of the station during the winter 2023/24.

and ± 1 m/s beyond 5 m/s. Its measurement range is 0 to 50 m/s, with a resolution of 0.1 m/s and a sensitivity threshold of 0.4 m/s. It functions within a temperature range of -30°C to $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The Kipp & Zonen CMP6 ISO First Class pyranometer measures reflected solar radiation. It has a measurement range of 0 to 1500 W/m^2 , and a linearity of 0.5%. The operating temperature ranges from -40°C to $+60^{\circ}\text{C}$, and maintenance includes changing hygroscopic salts.

The MTX precipitation sensor, model PPR with a calibrated 400 cm^2 mouth, is an unheated tipping bucket sensor made from anodized aluminum with dual magnetic contacts. The mouth is calibrated at 400 cm^2 , and the sensor offers an accuracy better than 1% at 24 l/h per m^2 . It has an unlimited measurement range, with a precision of 0.2 mm up to 50 mm. Its sensitivity threshold is 0.2 mm of rain or snow equivalent. The bucket is equipped with a leveling bubble, and it outputs through dual contacts. Since it is unheated, the available data for the winter season are not reliable and are not used in this work.

Therefore, the data at our disposal are: wind velocity and direction, air temperature, atmospheric pressure, incoming shortwave radiation (ISWR), relative humidity (RH), snow surface temperature, snowpack internal temperature, snow height and precipitation. The precipitation measurements during winters are not reliable since the bucket is not heated. Therefore, this quantity is never used in this work.

All instruments give a measurement average every hour except for the wind sensor that also gives the maximum as gust velocity, which are sent to the database and saved. Certainly, all the quantities exhibit different ranges and properties. It is essential to note that some quantities are often null with occasional spikes, such as precipitation, while others display daily and seasonal

oscillations, such as temperatures and radiations. For these reasons, the data go through a pre-processing that checks the physical limits of different quantities and also makes a cross check between related quantities, as precipitation and humidity. In this way errors and spikes are removed from the data. In the snow surface temperature, all the values above 0°C are removed since are not physically possible. Similarly, the increment of snow height is not taken if the relative humidity is smaller than 75%. However, the data has also been checked manually for anomalies.

Missing data came also from malfunctioning or interruption of communication. In this case there are various interpolation methods, the simplest of which is linear. For analysis and comparison, missing data periods are simply ignored. Given that the data set includes snow measurements, the data have been restricted to the period of the year when snow is present on the ground, losing around the 25% of the available data.

2.1.2 Numerical Weather Models and reanalysis

For this work the data from 2 different models and ERA5 reanalysis are available ¹. These are used to evaluate the one with output closest to the AWS and that produces the snowpack simulation most similar to the reference one, using the method developed here. The output for the desired location has been taken from the nearest grid point, without further interpolation. From all the models the quantity taken are: wind velocity and direction, air temperature, atmospheric pressure, incoming shortwave radiation (ISWR), relative humidity (RH), cloud cover (CLD) and precipitation amount (PSUM). To simplify the notation, ERA5 reanalysis will be addressed under the NWM category, serving the same purpose of the other two models. The characteristics of the three models are now presented and described in detail, highlighting the main differences.

NEMS4 The NOAA Environment Monitoring System (NEMS) is a fully compressible, Eulerian, nonhydrostatic dynamics solver with an option for hydrostatic simulations, designed for numerical weather prediction [27]. It prognoses variables such as horizontal wind components, temperature, hydrostatic and nonhydrostatic pressures, as well as scalars like turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) and water vapor. The model employs a rotated latitude-longitude grid for regional applications and a global latitude-longitude grid with polar filtering, combined with a hybrid terrain-following vertical coordinate that transitions to a pure pressure coordinate near the model top[28]. It utilizes Arakawa B-grid horizontal staggering and Lorenz vertical staggering, with time integration schemes that include forward-backward for fast waves, implicit for sound waves, Adams-Bashforth for horizontal advection, and Crank-Nicholson for

¹data provided by www.meteoblue.com

vertical advection. Conservation of mass, momentum, and energy is ensured, along with positive-definite and monotonic tracer advection. The model incorporates Smagorinsky nonlinear lateral diffusion, divergence damping, and supports initialization through GSI and the NEMS Preprocessing System (NPS). It allows for multiple nesting configurations and integrates WRF and GFS physical parameterizations for microphysics, cumulus, surface physics, and turbulence, making it a versatile tool for high-resolution weather and climate simulations. It is employed at different scales with various temporal and spatial resolutions. In this context, it has a 4 km horizontal grid (0.36°) over central Europe and 60 vertical levels, with a time resolution of 1 h and is used for a forecast of 72 h.

NEMSGLOBAL The structure of this model is the same of the previous but with a spatial resolution of 30 km and the same temporal one.

ERA5 Here, we document the ERA5 dataset, that is a high resolution realisation (referred to as "reanalysis" or "HRES") produced using 4D-Var data assimilation and model forecasts in CY41R2 of the ECMWF Integrated Forecast System (IFS), with 137 hybrid sigma/pressure (model) levels in the vertical and the top level at 0.01 hPa. Atmospheric data are available on these levels and they are also interpolated to 37 pressure, 16 potential temperature and 1 potential vorticity levels. "Surface or single level" data are also available, containing 2D parameters such as precipitation, top of atmosphere radiation and vertical integrals over the entire depth of the atmosphere. The atmospheric model in the IFS is coupled to a land-surface model (HTESSEL), which produces parameters such as 2m temperature and soil temperatures, and an ocean wave model (WAM), the parameters of which are also designated as "Surface or single level" parameters. Generally, the data are available at a subdaily and monthly frequency and consist of analyses and short (18 hours) forecasts, initialized twice daily from analyses at 06 and 18 UTC. Most of the analyzed parameters are also available from the forecasts. However, there are a number of forecast parameters, e.g. mean rates/fluxes and accumulations, that are not available from the analyses. The data are interpolated into a regular latitude / longitude grid with horizontal resolution 31 km, and the output is given with a temporal resolution of 1 h.

2.2 Snowpack simulation

To evaluate the characteristics of the snow accumulated at the ground, a one dimensional finite elements model named SNOWPACK is initialized either with the AWS data, ERA5 reanalysis and NWM outputs. The goal is to address the performance of SNOWPACK outputs and evaluate which input

gives the best representation of the simulation initialized with AWS data, which is taken as the reference.

SNOWPACK [29] is a one-dimensional snowpack structure model, developed at the Swiss Federal Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF) for avalanche warning purposes. SNOWPACK is a predictive model that uses Lagrangian finite elements to solve for heat and mass transfer, stresses and strains within the snowpack.

In SNOWPACK, snow is modeled as a three-phase (ice, water and air) porous medium, characterized by the volumetric contents of each phase and the microstructural parameters sphericity and dendricity, grain radius, bond radius and a grain type marker. These parameters are considered primary microstructural parameters because the temperature gradient and isothermal metamorphism routines determine the rates of change of these parameters over time. Additional microstructural parameters, such as the coordination number or the bond neck length, are termed secondary since they are calculated from the volumetric contents and primary microstructural parameters.

Snowpack performs physical modeling of the various processes taking place between the soil, snow cover and atmosphere in order to simulate the evolution of the snow cover based on meteorological input data.

Several kind of information need to be given to Snowpack for a simulation:

- the description of the place where the snow pack has to be simulated: latitude, longitude, elevation, slope;
- the time series of the various meteorological parameters
- the initial state of the various soil and snow layers.

In particular it requires the following meteorological parameters:

- air temperature (TA)
- relative humidity (RH)
- wind speed (VW)
- incoming short wave radiation (ISWR) and/or reflected short wave radiation (RSWR) or net short wave radiation (NET SW)
- incoming long wave radiation (ILWR) and/or surface temperature (TSS)
- precipitation (PSUM) and/or snow height (HS)
- ground temperature (TSG) or geothermal heat flux.

Now a brief description of how the model uses the meteorological data is presented.

Since the albedo is calculated by a statistical model, reflected or incoming shortwave radiation can be provided. According to the choice of boundary condition, incoming longwave radiation (or atmospheric emissivity) and/or snow surface temperature can be provided. If both are provided, the model uses snow surface temperature as long as it is well below melting temperature. In particular at the snowcover surface, either the measured surface temperature is prescribed (Dirichlet Boundary Conditions - DBC) or the meteorological parameters are used to determine a surface heat flux containing sensible and latent heat exchanges and a net longwave radiation contribution (Neumann boundary condition — NBC). For measured snow surface temperatures below -2°C , the DBC is used. As soon as the snow surface temperature reaches -2°C the model switches to the NBC. Shortwave radiation is modeled as a volumetric heat source. The intensity of the absorbed shortwave radiation decreases exponentially with distance below the surface. Phase changes between the ice and water components are also accounted for as volumetric heat sinks (melting) and sources (refreezing). Meltwater is transported via a simple threshold procedure: whenever the liquid water content in a layer exceeds the threshold value of currently 3%, the excess water is moved to the next layer. At the bottom, excess water can be discharged.

The settling of the snow, i.e. the height changes of the elements, is governed by a volumetric constitutive relation. For non-dendritic snow, the relation is linked to the microstructural parameters. It includes processes such as pressure sintering within the bonds and initial settling caused by surface tension. Provided that the model calculates a correct settling rate and that the corrected snow depth measurement is free of errors, the amount of new snow can be obtained by the following procedure. For every time step, the expected model snow depth, hs_{model} , without new snow precipitation is calculated and compared to the measured snow depth, hs_{valid} . The new snow height for this time step, hn , is then simply taken as the difference:

$$hn = hs_{valid} - hs_{model}. \quad (2.1)$$

The amount of new snow, hn , is added to the model as new elements. As a further check, this is only done if relative humidity is higher than 70% and reflected shortwave radiation is lower than 250 W/m^2 . It is obvious that this procedure adapts the model snow height to the measured snow height during periods of snowfall. A crucial part of the outlined procedure with respect to a correct total mass balance is, therefore, the estimation of the initial new snow density. The new snow density, ρ , is estimated using empirical relationship statistically derived in the form of a nonlinear combination. To avoid erroneous extrapolation, the density prediction is, thus, limited to a range from 30 to 150 kg/m^3 . This procedure ensures that for snow fall conditions there is no difference between modeled and measured snow depths. Of course, this comparison and adjustment is possible only for those stations for which the

snow height measurements are available. Otherwise, the hourly total precipitation is used to simulate the new snow, using meteorological parameters to learn its density. Furthermore, the viscosity formulation and also the effective thermal conductivity is conceived as a function of the metamorphic state of the snowpack.

In the end the model returns all the relevant dimensions for the entire profile at a hourly resolution. In figure 2.3 and 2.4 some of the output of the simulation with the AWS data from the winter 19/20 are shown.

2.2.1 Microphysics

By microstructure, it is meant the geometrical shapes that define the grain size, grain shape, pore size, pore shape and the nature of the intergranular bonding. Currently, SNOWPACK [30] uses four primary, i.e. independent microstructure parameters: sphericity, dendricity, grain size and bond size. All other microstructure parameters of SNOWPACK can be derived from these four parameters. An additional important property is the three-dimensional coordination number, which is currently a derived parameter. This is the number of bonds per grain and determines the interconnectivity of the ice matrix.

The snow microstructure varies through its metamorphism. As said, three types of metamorphism determine the continuous change of texture in deposited snow: equilibrium growth metamorphism, kinetic growth metamorphism and melt metamorphism. Equilibrium and kinetic growth metamorphism are governed by water vapor gradients between convex and concave surfaces and between ice matrix and pore space, respectively. Kinetic growth and wet metamorphism are very dynamic forms of metamorphism which cause rapid changes in the microstructure and material properties. In equilibrium growth the grain size change following the equation

$$\dot{r}_g(T, t) = sp \left(A_1 + \frac{A_2}{r_g} \right) e^{A_3 \left(\frac{1}{T_K} - \frac{1}{T} \right)}, \quad (2.2)$$

where A are empirical coefficients. Similarly, the bond size grows at the rate

$$\dot{r}_b(T, t) = B_1 \left(\exp - \frac{B_2}{r_n} - \exp - \frac{B_2}{r_g} \right) \exp B_3 (1/T_R - 1/T), \quad (2.3)$$

with T_R as reference temperature (273.15 K) and B parameters. Whereas, in kinetic growth the grain dimension depends on the water vapor flux \vec{J} :

$$\dot{r}_g(t) = \frac{a^2(t)J_L(t) + \frac{a^3(t)}{\Delta z} \Delta J_{L2L}(t)}{2f_{gg}\rho_i r_g(0)r_g(t)}. \quad (2.4)$$

Here, a is the lattice constant, J_{L2L} is the water vapor flux between different snow layers and J_L the grain-to-grain flux and f_{gg} is a geometrical factor taking

(a) Grain type

(b) Density

Figure 2.3: Two different quantities of the simulated snowpack for the winter 19/20 using the AWS data.

(a) Grain dimension

(b) Temperature

Figure 2.4: Two different quantities of the simulated snowpack for the winter 19/20 using the AWS data.

into account the real shape of the grain. Again for kinetic growth the rate of change for the bonds is:

$$r_b(t) = f_{gb} \frac{D p_v(t)}{\rho_i RT^2} \left[\frac{L}{RT} - 1 \right] \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}, \quad (2.5)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, L is the latent heat of sublimation, f_{gb} is a factor for grain-bond geometry and $\partial T/\partial z$ is the local temperature gradient across a bond. In these ways, the model determines the grain and bond size of each layer, which consequently change the microphysical properties.

The two remaining features are the dendricity and sphericity, which are parametrized using an index varying from 0 to 1. The new snow is considered to have a dendricity of 1 and a sphericity of 0.5. The change of this parameters depends on the temperature gradient and the grain type. In particular, the difference is between the new snow that tends to lose dendricity and has a sphericity changing rate depending on the dendricity and the old snow that has only a change in sphericity that depends on the temperature gradient only. The rate of change depends again on the temperature gradient and two regimes are distinguished for the case of dry new snow:

$$\dot{d}d(t) = \begin{cases} -2 \times 10^8 e^{-\frac{6000}{T}} \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right|, & \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right| \leq 5 \frac{K}{m} \\ -2 \times 10^8 e^{-\frac{6000}{T}} \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right|, & \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right| > 5 \frac{K}{m} \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

Here $\dot{d}d(t)$ has the unit (1/s). The change of sphericity is made dependent on the change of dendricity: The grains round as they loose their dendricity:

$$\dot{s}p(t) = \begin{cases} -0.3 \dot{d}d(t), & \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right| \leq 5 \frac{K}{m} \\ 0.3 \dot{d}d(t), & \left| \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right| > 5 \frac{K}{m} \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

Using the four primary microstructure parameters, as discussed above, many important features of snow can be described in a seasonal snow cover. These include the grain type classification following a separation with threshold on the different parameters, as shown in Fig 2.5. However, the set of parameters is incomplete in the sense that some of the snow changes that are observed and understood cannot be represented by those parameters. For example, melt-freeze crusts must also be represented. To overcome these shortcomings, a snow type marker that tracks the history of grain development is introduced.

To solve the bulk temperature equation, an estimation of the thermal conductivity of snow is required. The thermal conductivity must be parameterized including all heat transfer processes not explicitly modeled. Such processes are vapor transport across a pore space, or ventilation. Snow is modeled as a system of ice grains and pores in series and parallel with each other. Some of the heat conduction is through the ice, where the effect of the constriction induced by bonds and necks is taken into account: q_i , solid ice conduction from one

Figure 2.5: Grain classification scheme to translate the microstructure parameters into conventional grain types (source: [30]).

grain through a bond/neck into a neighboring ice grain. Another portion of the heat conduction is due to the transfer of heat from one ice grain across a pore space and then onto another ice grain: q_{ip} , series conduction of heat through a grain, then across a pore and again into another grain. The third portion of the transfer is associated with heat transfer within a pore which is large enough that the upper or lower bounding ice grain can be ignored: q_p , conduction purely across a pore. Radiation heat transfer across the pore space is not included as a significant factor. This model is extended to include the effect of liquid water in the pores. It is assumed that liquid water fills small pores as well as concave neck constrictions and therefore a fourth portion of heat conduction is introduced: q_{iw} , series conduction of heat through a grain, then across a pore (partly) filled with water and again into another grain. The capacity of the snow to hold liquid water is small enough that the larger pores will drain and are free of water. Therefore, the effective conductivity is taken from [31] and revised using a different conductivity of the pore space in parallel to the series and solid heat conduction. Furthermore, a heat pumping effect

is added to give the ultimate formula for effective conductivity:

$$k_e = \frac{n_{ca}}{n_{cl}} \left[\frac{\pi^2 r_b k_i N_3 F_k}{32} + \frac{k_a k_{ap} A_{ip}}{L_{is} k_{ap} + L_{ps} k_i} + \frac{k_a k_w A_{iw}}{L_{is} k_w + L_{ws} k_i} \frac{k_{ap} A_p}{L_p} \right], \quad (2.8)$$

where K are the single conductivity constant used together with some geometrical parameters as the lengths (L) and cross sections (A) of ice, liquid water and pores. Figure 2.6 schematizes all the possible heat transport medium modeled.

Figure 2.6: Types of heat conduction modes in the SNOWPACK conductivity model (source: [30]).

2.2.2 Parametrization

All snowpack simulations were performed using the SNOWPACK model presented in the previous chapter. The simulations forced with data from AWS and NWM are very similar in the parametrization. The main difference is that in the AWS data the snow height is used (as described) in forcing the simulated HS. Whereas using the NWMs data, the HS is retrieved by the precipitation. The simulations have been done using a time step of 15 minutes. The wind erosion is taken in to account and the canopy is modeled absent as the station is above the treeline. The stability of the atmosphere is modeled using the formulation of Holstg and De Burin [32]. The model is focused on calculating surface fluxes of sensible heat, latent heat, and momentum by using routine meteorological data. It is particularly applied to stable atmospheric conditions with low wind velocity. It uses a semi-empirical approach that links

surface fluxes to weather data like cloud cover, wind speed, air temperature, and humidity. The stability of the surface layer is expressed using the bulk Richardson number:

$$Ri_b = \frac{g\Delta\theta z}{\theta_0 U^2}, \quad (2.9)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, $\Delta\theta$ is the temperature difference, z is the height, θ_0 is the reference potential temperature and U is the wind speed. The stability of the boundary layer can also be described using the stability parameter (z/L):

$$\frac{z}{L} = \frac{zg\theta_0}{\theta_* u_*^2}, \quad (2.10)$$

where L is the Monin-Obukhov length describing the balance of mechanical and buoyant forces in the boundary layer, z is the height above the ground, θ_* is the temperature scale and u_* is the friction velocity. All the simulations used in this work are computed for the whole winter starting at the beginning of September.

2.3 Verification method

In this work, the verification of meteorological data from different NWMs and the snowpack simulations outputs are computed over different quantities, in different situations, and over different time spans. In order to allow direct, meaningful and complete comparison, some indices [33] are chosen and applied to every quantity taken into account. These are presented here and explained. The general aim is to compare data coming from NWMs with the AWS data as reference and to establish the similarity among these. The same is to be done with snowpack simulations run with AWS and NWMs data. Note that the information they provide are complementary and allow one to understand the type of error between observations and the model.

RMSE The root mean squared error of a set of N modeled values m_i against observations o_i is computed following:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^n (o_i - m_i)^2}{N}}. \quad (2.11)$$

It quantifies the difference between observed and predicted values, providing an overall measure of prediction accuracy. It calculates the square root of the average of squared differences between predicted and actual values, ensuring that larger errors are more heavily penalized. RMSE is particularly useful because it has the same units as the predicted variable, making it easy to interpret. On the other hand, this does not allow to average on different quantities errors to compute a mean model accuracy. Thereafter, the measure

of data spread is divided into two components: the systematic ($RMSE_s$) and the unsystematic ($RMSE_u$) ones [34]. Taking into account the observed and predicted data, these can be plotted in a scatterplot, and a linear regression can be computed. A perfect model should give a null intercept ($a = 0$) and an angular coefficient of one ($b = 1$). If the result of the fit is said $\widehat{m}_i = a + bo_i$ then the clearest form of the indexes are:

$$RMSE_S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N (\widehat{m}_i - o_i)^2}{N}} \quad (2.12)$$

and

$$RMSE_U = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N (m_i - \widehat{m}_i)^2}{N}}. \quad (2.13)$$

Defined in this way, $RMSE_S$ is the measure of the accuracy of the model and accounts for the systematic error of the predicted variable. This can be given by a pure bias (if $a \neq 0$ and $b = 1$) or by a generic error that can vary depending on the values (thus, b is not unitary). On the other hand, $RMSE_U$ measures the precision of the model and accounts for the variance of the data. These two together give the total RMSE and are always positive squared. This is positive since it allows for easier averaging, but also negative since it does not allow us to distinguish between an underestimation or an overestimation.

MBE The mean bias error gives the bias of the prediction model, actually computing the mean error [35]. The formula is:

$$MBE = \frac{\sum_i^N (m_i - o_i)}{N}. \quad (2.14)$$

Thus, a positive MBE implies an overestimation computed by the model, whereas if the index is negative the variable is underestimated.

SDoR The standard deviation of residuals reveals the precision of the model. A Gaussian distribution is not guaranteed for all the quantities considered but the residuals have this distribution. Therefore, computing the extent of the residuals (difference between the model and the observations) through the standard deviation, can give the extend of the spread of the data. In formula, this is:

$$SDoR = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N \left((m_i - o_i) - \overline{(m_i - o_i)} \right)^2}{N - 1}}. \quad (2.15)$$

This index is always positive and has the same dimension of the quantity considered.

d_r . The index of agreement [36] gives a measure of similarity between the predicted and observed values, varying between 1 and -1. It uses the mean absolute error and the mean absolute deviation, avoiding the square elevation that amplifies the high errors. Furthermore, the normalization depends only on the observations, allowing for a direct comparison between different models. In formula it is:

$$d_r = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{\sum |m_i - o_i|}{2 \sum |o_i - \bar{o}|}, & \text{when } \sum |m_i - o_i| \leq 2 \sum |o_i - \bar{o}| \\ \frac{2 \sum |o_i - \bar{o}|}{\sum |m_i - o_i|} - 1, & \text{when } \sum |m_i - o_i| > 2 \sum |o_i - \bar{o}| \end{cases}. \quad (2.16)$$

This depends on the ratio between the mean absolute error (MAE: $\sum |m_i - o_i|$) and the mean absolute deviation (MAD: $\sum |o_i - \bar{o}|$). Therefore, the higher is the value, the lower is the error that the model makes compared to the intrinsic variability of the considered quantity. Here, it is to be noted that this is the only adimensional index that allows a direct comparison between different dimensions and averages between these. Moreover, it is influenced by both the systematic and unsystematic errors. Since some quantities are subjected to oscillations at a daily or seasonally rate, this index is used with a moving average for \bar{o} for this quantities. However, it does not express the nature of the error. Thus, this index is very versatile and allow a overall comparison between datasets, also with good accuracy thanks to its wide range. On the other hand, it is not specific in the source of the error (as systematic or not) and can not distinguish between over- and under-estimation.

These indexes, as shown, have some pro and cons, that differ from one to the other. A good representation of the validation needs to consider different indexes to create a whole and deep evaluation. Only few of these has been used in the nivological field [37] [38] and often qualitative and visual comparisons only are used [39] [40] [41]. The aim of introducing these tested indexes is to deploy a quantitative validation method in the nivological field. The result is a robust, adaptable method that can be used also for the relevant meteorological quantities.

2.3.1 Meteorological data: AWS vs. NWM

All the models have been compared with the available data from the automatic weather station (AWS). The considered quantities are:

1. air temperature (TA);
2. west-est wind component (U);
3. south-nord wind component (V);
4. maximum wind speed (W_{max});

5. incoming shortwave radiation (ISWR);
6. relative humidity (RH).

Each of these quantities are compared using all the indexes presented over the whole period in which AWS data are available. This means from 04/10/2016 until March 2024, with a year of missing data resulting in 56400 measurements. In this case the graphical representation chosen is the scatterplot, since it allows for a direct comparison and is clear even over long period data.

2.3.2 Snow profiles

In the snowprofile the variables to be compared are numerous and some of them are strictly dependent on others and in the models are just retrieved from those. Furthermore, the comparison should be different depending on what it is aimed at (avalanche danger [42], model implementation, water availability, etc.). This comparison is general and oriented on the valuation of the overall performance. Thus the avalanche risk and stability indexes are not considered. The main quantities that describe the overall snowpack are: the temperature of snow surface (TSS), the snow height(HS) and the snow water equivalent (SWE). These are the results of energy and mass balance of the snowpack. The measure of these quantities brings one value for the whole snowpack; thus the data from the simulation are one every hour. Therefore, the indexes presented are computed over the time series and result in only one index for each dimension for the whole season.

Conversely, the other quantities are computed for every layer of the snowpack. These are:

1. grain type
2. grain size
3. hardness
4. liquid water content
5. temperature
6. density

In figure 2.7 three of the listed dimensions are shown on a snowprofile. The validation of these is done computing the indexes over the snowpack height, giving one value every simulated hour. Therefore, for each of these quantities there are a time series of every index for the whole winter. The season average of the indexes can be given to understand the mean performance of the simulation during the year. Otherwise, the full time series can be shown to highlight periods of different similarity between data.

Figure 2.7: Example of the simulated profile in one hour showing the grain type, hardness and temperature for the whole snowpack height.

The yearly profiles of the main quantities that are TSS, HS and SWE are compared using all the five different statistical method: the two root mean squared errors (RMSE) (systematic and unsystematic), the mean bias error (MBE), the standard deviation of the residuals (SDoR) and the index of agreement (d_r). In the end a scatterplot may be used to see the models performances and compare those together.

The comparison of the hourly profile is done evaluating all five indexes for every important characteristic of the snow to be compared. One exception is the grain type that is not numerical. For this quantity the comparison is evaluated using only a limited number of classified grain type. The table with empirically supported similarity is shown in 2.1.

Dynamic Time Warping The first problem encountered is how to compare different layers of the modeled and observed profiles. In general, the profile produced with AWS data and modeled ones can have shifted layers and slightly different thickness. Therefore, it is necessary to perform a mapping to match the layers and adjust the thickness. The first step is to adjust for potentially different snow heights in the modeled and observed profiles. This is done through a linear proportion between the modeled profile to be validated, called **query** and the one coming from the AWS data, called **reference**. The scaling factor is applied equally to all the layers of the query profile. Afterwards a Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm is used to match the different layers in the snowpack searching for the maximum similarity. This is a method for quantifying the dissimilarity between sequences that might vary in time or

	PP	DF	RG	FC	DH	SH	MF	FCxr	MFcr	na
PP	1.0									0.5
DF	0.8	1.0								0.5
RG	0.5	0.8	1.0							0.5
FC	0.2	0.4	0.4	1.0						0.5
DH	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	1.0					0.5
SH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.9	1.0				0.5
MF	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0			0.5
FCxr	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.0	0.0	1.0		0.5
MFcr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	1.0	0.5

Table 2.1: Similarity between grain type used for the comparison (source: [43]).

structure. DTW aligns elements from two sequences to minimize overall distortion, a crucial feature for applications like snow profile comparisons. The key steps in DTW involve building a local cost matrix \mathbf{D} that stores the distances between all possible element pairs from two sequences. In this case the local cost matrix is computed using the grain type, temperature and the hardness of both the query and reference profiles. Therefore, each element \mathbf{D}_{ij} of the local cost matrix \mathbf{D} can then be written as

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} = w_g d_g(q_i^g, r_j^g) + w_h d_h(q_i^h, r_j^h) + w_t d_t(q_i^t, r_j^t) + \eta(q_i^g, r_j^g), \quad (2.17)$$

where w_g , w_h , and w_t are averaging weights that sum up to 1 ($w_g + w_h + w_t = 1$) and d and η are functions that give the distance between different quantities of the query (q) and reference (r) profiles. In particular the superscripts g , h and t stands for graintype, hardness and temperature, respectively. The algorithm then seeks the optimal warping path P , which is the least-cost path through the matrix, adhering to several constraints.

Key constraints include monotonicity and continuity, ensuring that the path moves in a forward direction without retracing steps, and the use of a warping window to limit how far the alignment can deviate from the main diagonal. This avoids excessive warping and matches elements more meaningfully. The algorithm for the path used is the Sakoe-Chiba band [44], which restricts the path to a fixed-width diagonal region. The local slope constraint manages how many elements from one sequence can align with a single element from another, preventing excessive stretching or compression. In the context of snow profiles, this controls how much the thickness of snow layers is allowed to vary between profiles during alignment.

Another important feature is the handling of boundary conditions, where DTW can align sequences fully (matching start and end points) or partially. This flexibility allows DTW to be adapted to different use cases, such as comparing subsections of sequences or aligning specific portions (open-end or open-

Figure 2.8: The open-begin alignment of two query (\mathbf{Q}) and reference (\mathbf{R}) snow profiles: the line segments match the corresponding layers between \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} . Adjusting the layer thicknesses of profile \mathbf{Q} yields the warped profile \mathbf{Q}^w , which is optimally aligned to profile \mathbf{R} . At the top the legend for the grain type and at the bottom the hardness hand-test scale. (source:[43])

begin alignments). The objective remains finding the warping path that minimizes the total accumulated cost through the cost matrix, an optimization solved using dynamic programming.

This allows for a more accurate comparison because it arranges one layer with the corresponding one in the two profiles before evaluating the similarity. In this way it is possible to neglect layers that are not present in the reference profile and to adjust the thickness. The warping algorithm used is described in detail by [43]. The outcome is as shown in figure 2.8, where the warped query is the modeled profile after the adjustment performed by the DTW algorithm.

2.4 Precise point-to-point adjustment

Once the methodology to compare different meteorological and snow data is defined, we plan to improve the NWM data based on the measured ones. The ascertained method for doing this is using a downscaling method, which consists of an increase of spatial resolution of the data or in an adaptation of the data to a single known point. In the literature, there are many statistical methods for downscaling and adjusting models to measured data, most commonly used in climatology [45] [46] [47]. Some examples of these are bias correction, quantile mapping, weather generators, and others. Recently, neural networks

also found their application in this field [48] [49] [50]. Different deep learning architectures have been used for downscaling and forecasting[51], both in a spatial grid and at a single point [52].

2.4.1 Bias Correction

Most of the downscaling methods are applied in the retrieval of spatially distributed data. In this case, the reference is only a single AWS, so the whole process needs to rely on a single point. Furthermore, the quantities to be modified are multiple and this is not seen in the reported examples, where mainly precipitation alone was downscaled.

In this work, a bias correction is applied by linear regression for every quantity. Practically, from the dataset the period of one winter is removed and then, using all the remained data, the regression is applied according to the formula

$$X_{NWM} = mX_{AWS} + q, \quad (2.18)$$

where x are the data of a single quantity coming from the NWM or the AWS. In this way, the two parameters m and q are determined. The following step consists in using the parameters to correct the remaining data using

$$X_{BC} = (X_{NWM} - q)/m. \quad (2.19)$$

The corrected data for the selected winter are hereafter referred to as X_{BC} . These corrected data are then compared with the AWS data for the same winter to evaluate the extent to which the correction improves accuracy. Although this method is straightforward and computationally efficient, it does not provide adaptable corrections for different seasonal periods and meteorological conditions. Furthermore, this correction can only adjust the systematic error but not the spread and it does not account for interdependent influences among various atmospheric quantities, giving room for exploring possible alternatives as described in the following section.

2.4.2 Virtual Snow-Weather stations

Neural networks utilize large datasets to identify correlations, provide adaptability and flexibility, providing a valid alternative to classical statistical methods. In the literature, various deep learning approaches are applied in meteorological contexts, ranging from random forests [49] to convolutional networks [48], among others. The primary objective is to generate a time series that replicates the measurements using NWM data as input. Among the models tested and compared [53] [54] [55], the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) emerged as the most effective for time series generation [56], as it iteratively refines its outputs. Following the evaluation of the RNN's functionality,

the sequence-to-sequence (S2S) network was studied to achieve higher precision among networks with similar applications. The Sequence-to-Sequence architecture [57] appeared suitable for this purpose and was thus selected for comparison with the RNN.

The use of neural network in the meteorological field is not new but in this case the aim is to build a model that can use the dependencies between nivo-meteorological quantities to simulate all of these better and is not limited to single dimensions. This specific use is due to the need of a overall improvement in all considered quantities and not only a particular one. Therefore, both the model used have been adjusted for this purpose and are also flexible to adjust to different forecast periods, for example.

Recurrent Neural Network

The first implemented method is the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [58], utilizing the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)[59] algorithm. RNNs belong to a class of artificial neural networks designed for processing sequential data by retaining a hidden state that captures information from previous time steps [56]. Traditional RNNs face the problem of vanishing gradients [60], which limits their ability to capture long-range dependencies within sequences.

LSTM addresses the limitations of traditional RNNs by maintaining a cell state and employing a set of gates (input, forget, and output) to regulate information flow, facilitating better retention of crucial information across longer sequences. An LSTM-based RNN comprises multiple LSTM cells arranged sequentially. Each cell processes input data from the current time step and hidden state from the preceding time step to update its internal state. The output of each LSTM cell serves as the hidden state input for the subsequent time step, enabling information propagation across multiple time steps. This architecture allows LSTM networks to overcome the issues of traditional RNNs, such as vanishing gradients, by enabling effective learning over long time horizons. Overall, LSTM-based RNNs excel in capturing long-term dependencies, managing variable-length sequences, and adapting to changing patterns, making them potent tools for various time series analysis tasks like forecasting, anomaly detection, and sequence classification. This makes LSTM particularly well-suited for time series data, as it can handle sequential patterns and temporal dependencies, even when the relationships span across long intervals of time. For this specific application, the chosen design entails an LSTM layer followed by a Dense layer and concludes with a reshape operation, as illustrated in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9: The simple structure of the RNN used.

The model is compiled using Mean Squared Error as the loss function and Adamax optimizer [61] with a learning rate of 0.005. These choices were made, following multiple attempts, to optimize model performance by minimizing the discrepancies between NWM and AWS data rather than focusing solely on overall error. Model performance is evaluated using Mean Absolute Error. Hyperparameters, including LSTM units and learning rate are determined using the KerasTuner tool [62], specifically employing the Hyperband tuner [63]. Training is carried out over 50 epochs with a batch size of 32, using 70% of available data for each model and AWS. A sample learning curve of the training process is shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: Learning curve of the training process.

Sequence to sequence

The aim of improving the results led to the exploration of another model commonly used for time series analysis: the sequence-to-sequence (Seq2Seq) model. Seq2Seq models [64] belong to a class of neural networks designed to map sequences from one domain to sequences in another domain. They consist of two primary components: an encoder and a decoder. During training, the input sequence is fed into the encoder, which processes it and generates a fixed-length representation known as a context vector. This context vector serves as the initial state for the decoder. The decoder then utilizes this context vector to generate an output sequence, one element at a time [65]. Seq2Seq models are powerful tools for modeling and generating sequential data. By leveraging the encoder-decoder architecture, they can handle various tasks involving sequences of variable lengths [66]. The design of the sequence-to-sequence model with LSTM encoder and decoder is illustrated in Figure 2.11. The compilation

Figure 2.11: The design of the sequence to sequence model with LSTM encoder and decoder.

and training processes are conducted similarly as before, with a learning rate of 0.01, a batch size of 32, and 50 epochs. The learning curve obtained during training is depicted in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Learning curve of the Seq2Seq model on the VALL station data.

Another preprocessing step involves substituting the snow height (HS) with Δ_{HS} , defined as the difference between the current HS and the previous one. This adjustment is made because HS typically undergoes gradual changes and is not strictly correlated with any other variable in its absolute value but rather with its variations (e.g., precipitation and wind). Following this, normalization of all used data is performed using the max-min range method to ensure that all values fall within the range of 1 to 0. To train the neural network models, the entire dataset is divided into short sequences of 24 hours, referred to as windows. This choice is made to configure the model for daily predictions and adjustments.

Chapter 3

Results and discussion

In this chapter, the results of the NWMs validations are presented, both before and after bias correction. Thereafter, the snowpack simulations outputs are compared with the reference one, initialized with AWS data.

3.1 Raw NWMs data

Here the different NWM data are compared with the station measurements for the entire available period. This stage is simple, but very important to understand which model simulates the atmospheric conditions more similar to the station. Firstly, we will compare the meteorological quantities used in the snow simulation. Later, the snow simulations are computed and the outputs are compared to see which NWM produce the snow profile closest to the reference one. Finally, we investigate the role of each meteorological quantity for the snowpack.

3.1.1 Meteorological data

Firstly, we see the scatterplot of the different considered quantities in figure 3.1 and 3.2.

Here, the quantities have different spreads in relation to the AWS data and between them. However, from the plots it is difficult to quantify the discrepancies to define the best model. Thus, the index d_r is evaluated for every quantity of all the NWMs compared with the AWS data. Remember that this index is computed as the ratio of the mean absolute error (MAE) by the mean absolute deviation (MAD), transposed to vary in the interval between 1 (no error) and -1 (big error). Note that therefore, negative values do not account for underestimation (not verifiable with this index) but for MAE greater than the MAD, thus poor accuracy. For TA and ISWR, the MAD is computed over the moving average with a period of one week to account for seasonal oscillations. From the values of d_r in table 3.1, it appears clear

(a) Air temperature.

(b) Incoming shortwave radiation.

Figure 3.1: Scatterplots showing the raw meteorological data from AWS and models.

(a) Relative humidity.

(b) Wind velocity.

Figure 3.2: Scatterplots showing the raw meteorological data from AWS and models.

d_r	ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
TA	0.38	0.52	0.59
U	0.42	-0.06	0.28
V	0.41	-0.07	0.27
RH	0.66	0.69	0.59
ISWR	0.86	0.85	0.84
Mean	0.46	0.32	0.43

Table 3.1: Values of the index of similarity d_r for all dimensions compared for all NWMS and their mean.

that NEMS4 is the worst in reproducing the overall quantities in the AWS location. ERA5 appears to be slightly better than NEMSGLOBAL on average. However, it is important to note that this ranking is not reflected in the single quantities for which the models have different performances: all three models are similar for RH and ISWR, ERA5 is not as good as the others for TA but the best for the winds components. One important fact to point out is that in the meteorological analysis the precipitation amount is missing because of the data dearth.

Now, it can be interesting to better analyze the reasons for such different performances in all the quantities. To do so, the RMSE systematic and unsystematic can provide insight into the different natures of the error.

TA	ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
$RMSE_S$ [K]	3.02	2.44	1.52
$RMSE_U$ [K]	3.34	1.94	2.50

Table 3.2: Values of the indexes for the air temperature to show the influence of different error sources.

Air temperature The indexes shown in Table 3.2 explain better the distances between models and measures. ERA5 has a high systematic error, which stems from a strong bias. At the same time, the $RMSE_U$ is also high, which shows that the precision of the model is low. These two errors both decrease for the other two models but in different ways. NEMS4 has the lowest spread in the data and NEMSGLOBAL has the lowest bias. Overall, the best simulated temperature is given by NEMS GLOBAL, even though in general the systematic error is easier to correct.

Wind components A similar analysis can be performed for wind components (Table 3.3), showing that all the models have a similar bias and they differ by the spread that is small for ERA5 and large for the NEMS4 results. Here, we can see that the systematic error is less than 2 m/s that is not large

		ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
U	$RMSE_s$	1.90	1.93	1.90
	$RMSE_u$	1.01	3.83	1.83
V	$RMSE_s$	1.89	1.85	1.91
	$RMSE_u$	1.04	3.86	1.86

Table 3.3: Values of the indexes for the wind components to show the influence of different error sources.

and easily corrigible. On the other hand, the unsystematic errors vary a lot between models and are really relevant for NEMS4, that results the worst for wind modeling followed by NEMS GLOBAL. Since the evaluation is done with the components, the results strongly depend on the direction of the winds that are influenced by the orography in the alpine environment. More specifically, at this resolution the evaluation of the wind components can be erroneous if the point of extrapolation of the model and the AWS location do not coincide. In the case of GESS, the station is protected by mountains in the north-northeast sides and therefore is complicated that models with coarse resolution as LAM or global can catch the local wind behaviour.

Relative humidity For relative humidity, the values in table 3.4 are similar, except for the NEMS GLOBAL that has a significantly larger systematic error. In this case, NEMS4 has the best results, close to ERA5.

RH	ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
$RMSE_S$	0.05	0.05	0.15
$RMSE_U$	0.16	0.15	0.16

Table 3.4: Values of the indexes for the air temperature to show the influence of different error sources.

Incoming shortwave radiation The values for the ISWR (table 3.5) are very different between systematic and unsystematic ones. The $RMSE_S$ has small values for ERA5 and NEMS4. On the contrary, the unsystematic part has similar values for all the models, around 100 [W/m^2]. Here, the model

TA	ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
$RMSE_S$ [W/m^2]	7	15	59
$RMSE_U$ [W/m^2]	101	110	102

Table 3.5: Values of the indexes for the air temperature to show the influence of different error sources.

that has the best results is ERA5.

3.1.2 Snow profiles

Now the comparison between the different snow profiles simulated with the different meteorological data as input is presented. Here, the profiles are simulated winter by winter for all four sets of forcing data available, namely: AWS, ERA5, NEMS4 and NEMSGLOBAL. The validation, evaluated the presented indexes, is done using the simulation done with the AWS data as reference. The best results are expected from the simulations initialized with the ERA5 data, since is the one with values closer to the AWS ones.

However, it is possible that some differences on more than one quantity even out and so that a model that is not very close to the measurements brings to a better snowpack simulation. Furthermore, the meteorological comparison is made over the whole data period, including six different winters, whereas the snow comparison is done winter by winter, and thus the simulation performance may vary from year to year. In addition, different quantities have different influences on the snowpack simulation. Therefore, a model that has poor performance in specific dimensions may lead to good simulations.

As general evaluation of the simulations, we can directly watch the simulated snow surface temperature (Fig. 3.4) and snow height (Fig. 3.3) in two different winters. In the winter 16/17 (Fig 3.3a), HS is poorly modeled by NEMS4 dataset that has a strong overestimation. The other two models have values close to the AWS measured HS, but with great spread, both positive and negative. This changes in the winter 22/23 (Fig 3.3b) that is better modeled and with similar behaviour from all the simulations. HS is overestimated in all three simulations, less in the NEMS GLOBAL compared to the others.

In the scatterplot of TSS for the 16/17 winter (Fig. 3.4a) the spread of all simulations is clear, limited only for NEMS4 dataset. The presence of biases is evident, mainly at low temperatures where the mean of simulated values is lower than the AWS ones. The simulation done with ERA5 dataset has the most distinct underestimation, in both winters. In fact, the characteristics of the simulations remain the same in winter 22/23 (Fig. 3.4b) but with a overall decreased bias, also at low temperatures. NEMS4 has the least spread as before whereas ERA5 has still a defined underestimation. NEMS GLOBAL has a moderate spread and possibly a slight overestimation.

In order to quantify the performances of the simulations, the indexes are used for every quantity, using the simulation done with the AWS data as reference. Initially, the index of agreement d_r was calculated for the yearly time series of TSS, HS, and SWE. For every dimensions on the snowprofile, d_r is evaluated every hour along the height of the snowpack. Thereafter, the mean of all the values is computed to obtain the agreement during the winter, for each quantity. It has to be noted that the negative values of d_r do not imply an underestimation (since the errors are taken as mean absolute values) but a large error of the model (grater then the MAD of the reference dataset). For the grain type validation the similarity index is used since this dimension

(a) Winter 16/17.

(b) Winter 22/23.

Figure 3.3: Time series of snow height.

is not numerical. Ultimately, the mean of all dimension values for every year is calculated for all three models and shown in figure 3.5. The bar plot shows that some years are better represented than others, also varying from model to model. For simplicity, the mean of all years is shown in table 3.6. This results show that on average the best model used as input for the simulation is NEMS4. At first sight, it can seem that this result contradicts the previous one. However, the simulations use the precipitation from the NWM, which is a quantity that cannot be validated against the AWS data. This implies a source of uncertainty in the evaluation of the NWMs done before. Moreover, in the meteorological comparison it is clear that wind estimation significantly affects the final performance. So, a more accurate analysis can be done to better understand the situation and which simulated quantities are ruined by these errors. To begin with, the time averages of the similarity index for each

Figure 3.4: Scatterplots of snow surface temperature.

	ERA5	NEMS4	NEMSGLOBAL
d_r	0.00	0.08	0.05

Table 3.6: Whole period mean of the similarity index, for all dimensions.

nivological dimension are shown for each model (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Average over the six considered winters of the d_r index (the similarity index is used for grain type) for every dimension. Namely: density, grain size, grain type, hardness, snow height, liquid water content, snow water equivalent, temperature (meant as internal of every snow layer) and snow surface temperature.

Figure 3.5: For the three models the yearly mean values of d_r are shown

Here, in general it is evident that some quantities are harder to be modeled using NWMs inputs, as HS and SWE. It is important to remember that for grain type d_r can not be used since it is not numerical and so here the similarity index ranging from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (total agreement) and based on the matrix (Fig. 2.1) is used. Looking more in detail, the simulations with NEMS4 are better for most of the dimensions or close to the others simulations. The only exception is for HS in which the model performs significantly worse.

At this point, it may be interesting to study the different quantities in more depth, using also other indexes if needed.

Snow height In figure 3.7 the d_r index for HS is shown for every winter without any averaging. Here, it can be seen that the poor performance of the

Figure 3.7: The values of d_r for HS evaluated every winter.

simulation of the HS using NEMS4 as input is constant over the whole period. Now, for further understanding, the other presented indexes are evaluated and presented to understand the source of error that seems to be constant. Exactly, to make the average for the entire winter, $RMSE_S$ and $RMSE_U$ are used and displayed in figure 3.8a and 3.8b, respectively. Here, we can see that on average

(b) $RMSE_U$.

Figure 3.8: Comparison of snow height RMSE evaluated over all the winters.

the systematic error is greater compared to the unsystematic one. Both types of error are larger for the simulations done using NEMS4 data in most cases. It could be interesting to see the value of the bias (tab 3.7) and the evolution of HS (fig. 3.9) during one of the worst winters, as 19/20. Here, NEMS4 has a strong positive bias, probably due to an overestimation of precipitation combined to an underestimation of solar radiation, since the melting has a low rate. In the opposite way, NEMS GLOBAL has a negative bias, but similarly has a slow melting.

Figure 3.9: Snow height during winter 19/20 as measured by AWS and modeled with different NWMs data.

	ERA5	NEMS GLOBAL	NEMS4
MBE	0.25 m	-0.21 m	0.81 m

Table 3.7: Bias of the HS in the winter 19/20 for the three simulations

Snow Surface Temperature The comparison of TSS is shown in figure 3.10, where the performance during every winter is reported.

Figure 3.10: The values of d_r for TSS evaluated every winter.

Here it is clear that ERA5 data simulates poorly the temperature at the top of the snowpack, given the little similarity. This is logical given that the air temperatures had low similarity in the meteorological comparison. The two NEMS models have similar performance with a slightly better precision for

NEMS4, for most of the years. From the systematic and unsystematic errors, show in figure 3.11a and 3.11b respectively, we can see that the spread or unsystematic error is similar for all the models, around 5 K, for every winter. Whereas, the bias is considerably larger for the ERA5 simulations in every winter, justifying the poor overall performance.

(b) $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.11: Comparison of snow surface temperature root mean square errors evaluated for all the winters.

Snow Water Equivalent The SWE validation is shown in figure 3.12. The constantly poor performance of all the models is attributable to the one in snow height (Fig. 3.7). This is because the equivalent water quantity contained in the snowpack is directly dependent on how much snow is present, given by the HS.

Similarly to HS, the systematic error (Fig. 3.13a) is large except for the last two years and the unsystematic one (Fig. 3.13) is much greater in the NEMS4 simulations. The reasons of these are to be searched in the HS and density analysis.

Figure 3.12: The values of d_r for SWE evaluated every winter.

(a) $RMSE_S$

Figure 3.13: $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.14: Comparison of snow water equivalent root mean square errors evaluated for all the winters.

Density The results of the simulated density validation in figure 3.15 show a variable performance over the winters.

Figure 3.15: The values of d_r for density evaluated every winter.

NEMS4 values are overall the best passed by the NEMS GLOBAL only for a couple of years. Studying the detailed $RMSE_S$ (Fig. 3.16a) and $RMSE_U$ (Fig. 3.16b) allow to see that most of the error comes form the systematic one or bias.

(a) $RMSE_S$

(b) $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.16: Comparison of density evaluated for all the winters.

Figure 3.17: Evolution of the Mean Bias Error evaluated along the snowpack, for the 18/19 winter.

This is also the most variable through the years. The spread is overall constant around 30 kg/m^3 for all the years, with a tendency to decrease in the last years and a single spike for NEMS4 in the winter 22/23.

It could be interesting to deepen the knowledge of the bias in the worst year, 18/19. To do this, the time series of the MBE along that winter is shown in figure 3.17.

Here, NEMS4 data oscillates around zero, meaning low bias on hourly average. NEMS GLOBAL and ERA5 produce simulations with underestimation of the snow density along the whole winter. One key common behaviour is the underestimation of the density during the melting period which emphasizes the difficulty to model the thaw, both in timing and dynamic.

Grain Type The values of the similarity index (Fig. 3.18) for the grain type are more or less constant around 0.5 and similar among the three models.

Figure 3.18: The values of similarity index for grain type evaluated every winter.

A poor performance is evident for NEMS models in the first winter. The

overall score around 0.5 is not good, considering the discrete nature of the quantity and the scores given by the index. It is interesting to see the evolution of the index along the winter (Fig. 3.19), that is thus only averaged over the single snowprofile. The evolution shows that the performance of NEMS4 is

Figure 3.19: Evolution of the similarity index for the grain type along the winter 18/19.

better than the others for all the season. In the melting period, the index drops for all the models and later raises immediately to the top for the end of the thaw. This is simply due to the delay in the simulation of the melting (that affects the density, too) and therefore snow profiles containing grain types different from the melt form (MF), that has similarity null with all other types (Tab. 2.1).

Grain Size Evaluating the d_r index for the grain size, the performance (Fig. 3.20) is confused along the years and for the models. This makes hard to

Figure 3.20: The values of d_r for grain size evaluated every winter.

make any satisfying analysis. Perhaps, the detailed study of systematic and

unsystematic error can give some useful insights. These are plotted in figure 3.21a and 3.21b, respectively.

(b) $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.21: Comparison of grain size RMSE evaluated for all the winters.

Studying the different errors separately, it is clear that for every winter NEMS4 has the least error. Moreover, the bias and spread have always comparable values.

Hardness The performance of the models in the simulation for the hardness is shown in figure 3.22 and it appears without precise patterns or specific models that has greater similarity to the reference.

Figure 3.22: The values of d_r for hardness evaluated every winter.

Looking at the $RMSE_S$ in figure 3.23a, NEMS4 seems to have the least bias over different years. The $RMSE_U$ in figure 3.23b does not add much information except some large errors from ERA5 and NEMS GLOBAL simulations.

(a) $RMSE_S$

(b) $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.23: Comparison of hardness evaluated for all the winters.

Overall, there is a good performance for all the three models in the winters 18/19, 19/20 and 21/22.

Liquid Water Content The values of d_r for the liquid water content, shown in figure 3.24, vary from year to year with the NEMS4 simulation as the only always positive. As average, the systematic error (Fig. 3.25a) seems to be

Figure 3.24: The values of d_r for LWC evaluated every winter.

bigger than the unsystematic one (Fig. 3.25). NEMS4 has small $RMSE_U$ value in general but high $RMSE_S$ ones, compared to the others.

(a) $RMSE_S$

Figure 3.25: $RMSE_U$

Figure 3.26: Comparison of LWC RMSE evaluated for all the winters.

Overall, the values are considerable since are near to the LWC that the layers can retain (between 3 and 6%).

Following the observations and considerations made in this section, the NEMS4 model was selected for adjustment using the methods presented. This selection is due to the fact that the low performance observed at the meteorological level can be mainly attributed to the wind components. However, from a nivological perspective, the simulations initiated with these data are marginally superior overall. In most of the quantities, the model have similar performances. In those where some important differences are present, NEMS4 has the least error (TSS, temperature, grain type) Additionally, a significant source of error arises from snow height, which is directly modeled in the adjustments made through the neural network models. Consequently, these simulations have the potential for greater improvement relative to others.

3.2 Bias corrected NWM

Here, we present the same analysis as before on the adjusted meteorological data from the NEMS4 model as described in 2.4.1. The NEMS4 model is chosen as the best according to the results of the previous analysis on meteorological and nivological data. From now on, the study is limited to the winter of 19/20 and all other data are used to calibrate the correction models presented in 2.4. The choice of the year to be used is simply done taking one of the worst simulations to see which improvement could be done. Among these, the chosen one is studied a bit deeper than the others in the previous section, allowing for an extensive comparison.

3.2.1 Meteorological data

The method of data correction is more applicable to certain quantities than to others due to the various errors and discrepancies between the modeled and measured data. The linear regression graph (Fig. 3.27) highlights the variation in data distribution and shows how applying bias correction can improve data accuracy. For instance, in figure 3.27a, the limited spread of TA allows the correction to address the model's underestimation of temperatures, as evidenced by the value of the fit intercept q in table 3.8. Conversely, the ISWR data exhibit a greater spread (Fig. 3.28) and a significant underestimation, shown by the angular coefficient $m = 0.74$.

	TA	RH	ISWR	VW	VW-MAX
m	1.0	0.85	0.74	1.11	0.87
q	-1.4 K	0.14 %	0.0 w/m^2	0.96 m/s	1.12 m/s

Table 3.8: Coefficients of the linear regression for every quantity.

Figure 3.27: Scatterplots with line of the fit for the linear regression.

The applied technique corrects the bias without altering the spread of the data. Consequently, we presume a reduction in MBE and $RMSE_S$, while $SDoR$ and $RMSE_U$ are expected to remain relatively stable.

In the table 3.8 all the values of the linear regression are shown. From these, all the biases can be understood and quantified. For example, both wind velocity and gust velocity are overestimated by 1 m/s on average. In contrast, air temperature has a negative bias.

Comparing the outputs of the BC method with the AWS data for the same period, we obtain the results resumed in table 3.9. The performance of the model is good for TA, ISWR and RH with a D_r index above 0.6. As expected, the main source of error is found in the unsystematic component, which results in $SDoR$ and $RMSE_U$ higher than MBE and $RMSE_S$. The wind components

Figure 3.28: Scatterplot of ISWR max with the linear regression for the BC.

remain with great discrepancy with high spread.

$NEMS_{BC}$	TA	ISWR	RH	U	V
d_r	0.68	0.66	0.68	0.13	0.09
MBE	-0.57	56	0.03	0.00	-0.02
SDor	2.12	206	0.18	4.04	4.06
$RMSE_S$	0.35	73	0.04	2.09	2.04
$RMSE_U$	2.14	227	0.18	3.46	3.50

Table 3.9: Indexes resulting from the validation of the NEMS4_BC over the AWS data.

Comparing this with the raw data of the same year using the D_r index we obtain the figure 3.29. Here, again the greater improvement are visible in the quantities in which initially there was a strong bias, as TA and ISWR. The wind is also improving, but starting from a poor performance, it remains not well modeled.

Figure 3.29: The d_r index for all the quantities simulated by NEMS4 and NEMS_BC are compared.

3.2.2 Snow profiles

Now that the different meteorological quantities have been validated, we can proceed with the snowpack simulation and see how the improvements in the meteorological data affect it. Starting from the overall validation, table 3.10 shows a good improvement in the mean that is also reflected in every dimension except TSS that has a slight reduction. This means that the correction has

d_r	NEMS4_BC	NEMS4
HS	-0.71	-0.88
SWE	-0.73	-0.91
TSS	0.39	0.40
Temp	0.57	0.45
LWC	0.65	0.07
Density	0.70	0.56
Hardness	0.60	0.26
gsize	0.01	-0.06
gtype	0.74	0.52
Mean	0.25	0.05

Table 3.10: The index D_r for every quantity averaged along the winter.

good effects on the simulation overall. The snow surface temperature do not improve using this method. To check this, the scatterplot is shown in figure 3.30. Here, it can be seen that the problem in this case is the spread of the data that do not improve using this method.

Deepening the analysis, the *RMSE* indexes are computed and shown in figure 3.31. Here, we can see that for different quantities the systematic and unsystematic errors vary in different ways. The snow height, for example, improves in the systematic error. This can also be seen in the evolution of HS

Figure 3.30: Scatterplot of the snow surface temperature, with and without the BC correction.

Figure 3.31: Both the systematic and unsystematic parts of RMSE for all dimensions before and after the bias correction.

Figure 3.32: Evolution of the snow height during the winter 19/20 as modeled with and without bias correction.

during winter, in figure 3.32. In this graph, we can see that the snowfall and accumulation has the same overestimation than before, since the precipitation could not be adjusted for data unavailability. However during thaw, the melting is better modeled, probably due to the adjustment over the ISWR that was underestimated and improved after this adjustment.

Moreover, it could be interesting to consider the evolution of different errors during winter as well. For example, the hardness has the same systematic error as before and a strong decrease in $RMSE_U$. Investigating the evolution of MBE and $SDoR$ during winter can highlight periods of better performance than others. The MBE (Fig. 3.33) in the simulation after the BC has a low underestimation during the whole winter. In the melting period, the bias oscillates around zero, probably due to the error in the simulated thickness of the melting layer. This means that during the whole winter the average along the snowprofile of the hardness simulated with this data is a little less than the reference one. Repeating the same analysis over the $SDoR$ (Fig. 3.34), the spread variability along the winter can be assessed. Here, the simulation done with and without BC have different trends in the beginning and the same uncertain performance during thaw. This last problem could refer to the creation and melting of crusts during nights and cold periods that depend on slight atmospheric temperature differences. Here, we can see that the improvement of the hardness simulation is greater in the unsystematic error and this is the reason why the $RMSE_U$ has such a drop in figure 3.31.

In summary, the bias correction method is able to address different errors as over- and under-estimation, and this has good results in the snow simulations.

Figure 3.33: Evolution of the MBE for hardness during the winter 19/20.

Figure 3.34: Evolution of the $SDoR$ for hardness during the winter 19/20.

However, quantities dependent on precipitation, such as snow height and SWE, and highly spread data suffer little improvement.

Chapter 4

The breakthrough of Neural Network

After the promising improvements provided by bias correction methods, we want to deepen the precision adjustment using more complex methods. The neural network (NN) models presented in Sec. 2.4.2 are trained to adjust the NWMs meteorological data over the AWS ones. Two different models are used in this section: the recurrent neural network and sequence-to-sequence, labeled RNN and S2S after their structures. The adaptability of NN allow them to be trained also to model different quantities measured by the AWS. In this work, both models are trained to simulate the snow surface temperature and the snow height. Simulated TSS is used in all simulations as measured data. While as for HS, two SNOWPACK simulations have been done for every model: with and without HS forcing. The result of the forced simulation are presented later and the data are labeled as "_hs".

The validation of both meteorological and nivological quantities is done using the statistical indexes (d_r , $RMSE$, MBE and SDoR) and direct comparison. The data used for reference are the measurements from the AWS and the snowpack simulation forced with these.

4.1 Meteorological data

The validation of the atmospheric quantities is made as in the previous section. The available data are from the whole 19/20 winter, the models are trained with the data from 16/17, 17/18, 18/19, 21/22 and 22/23 winters. Actually, the 10 % of these are used for testing the models. Therefore, the data span from the 1st November 2019 to the 15th June 2020. For a direct comparison with the previous method, the data coming from the BC section are kept.

Starting from an overall comparison, in figure 4.1 the index of agreement d_r for every dimension is shown. In this barplot, the improvement given by the NN models is evident compared to both the NWM and the BC corrected data.

Figure 4.1: The index d_r for all the meteorological quantities and the different correction models.

For air temperature and wind components, the difference are remarkable. For TA the gain between the raw NEMS4 data and RNN is $\Delta d_r = 0.31$; for the wind components $d_r \approx 0.4$. After the NN models precision adjustment, all dimensions have good performance. Only the wind, despite the great improvement, does not have large d_r values. Now it is interesting to see in detail how the single dimensions improve.

Air Temperature Air temperature is among the dimensions that have good improvement with all the adjustment methods, especially with NNs. The evolution of the weekly averaged TA in the winter is shown in figure 4.2. It can

Figure 4.2: Weekly averaged air temperature from NEMS4 and all correction methods used.

be seen that both NEMS4 raw and BC adjusted data have strong underesti-

Figure 4.3: Scatter plot of air temperature from NEMS4 and all correction methods used.

TA	NEMS4	BC	RNN	S2S
$RMSE_S$ [K]	2.8	0.4	0.4	0.6
$RMSE_U$ [K]	2.1	2.2	1.7	1.6

Table 4.1: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values for different models (NEMS4, BC, RNN, and S2S) for air temperature.

mation along the whole winter, whereas the NN adjusted data have limited and smaller deviation from the measurements. In the scatter plot (Fig. 4.3) the spread decreases as the complexity of the adjustment increases. The S2S values are those with the least spread, as can be understood from the table 4.1. Here, the unsystematic error drops for the NN models, whereas the bias is comparable to the one obtained with BC method.

Incoming Shortwave Radiation Regarding the incoming shortwave radiation, the scatterplot in figure 4.4 shows a remarkable decrease in the spread of the data between NEMS4 and NN methods, especially for the low values. This may be due to the information coming from other quantities as humidity and cloud cover that directly influence the absorption of radiation in the atmosphere and are used in the NN models. The values of $RMSE_S$ and $RMSE_U$ contained in table 4.2 quantify this improvement in the spread. The systematic error is to be noted. It is more or less constant among the models except for RNN adjustment that has a larger bias. Apparently, this is not significant, compared with the improvement obtained in the spread.

Figure 4.4: Scatter plot of ISWR from NEMS4 and all correction methods used.

ISWR	NEMS4	BC	RNN	S2S
$RMSE_S$ [W/m^2]	15	13	41	11
$RMSE_U$ [W/m^2]	180	99	89	87

Table 4.2: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values for different models (NEMS4, BC, RNN, and S2S) for incoming shortwave radiation (ISWR).

Relative Humidity The relative humidity is the quantity better modeled in the NEMS4 data, to the extent that the BC correction do not make any improvement overall (Fig. 3.29). The NN adjustment methods manage to decrease the overestimation that is present in the raw data. This can be seen in the weekly averaged plot in figure 4.5. From the scatter plot of RH (Fig. 4.6), it seems that using the NN adjustment methods the spread is reduced but a slight underestimation is introduced by S2S model. Looking with more attention through the $RMSE$ indexes (Tab. 4.3) the spread decreases for NN methods but not for BC. The bias, on the other hand, is small for the BC and

RH	NEMS4	BC	RNN	S2S
$RMSE_S$	0.09	0.04	0.4	0.06
$RMSE_U$	0.16	0.18	0.11	0.10

Table 4.3: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values for different adjustment methods (NEMS4, BC, RNN, and S2S) for relative humidity (RH).

RNN methods, whereas for the S2S it improves less.

Figure 4.5: Winter evolution of the weekly averaged relative humidity, as modeled using the NEMS4 model and all three adjustment methods.

Figure 4.6: Scatter plot of relative humidity from NEMS4 and all correction methods used.

Wind Components The winds simulated from NEMS4 have the problem to be overestimated. The BC method could not improve much this error and left the spread unchanged. In the graphs, for clarity, the module of wind velocity (VW) is used. It is computed as $VW = \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}$. The NN methods manage to decrease the deviation as shown in the time series in figure 4.7. In the scatter

Figure 4.7: Evolution of the wind velocity in the winter 19/20, as modeled by NEMS4 and adjusted using the three methods.

plot in figure 4.8, the overestimation of the models turns in an underestimation. Whereas, the spread is significantly reduced. This is quantified by the *RMSE*

Figure 4.8: Scatter plot of wind velocity from NEMS4 and all correction methods used.

values in table 4.4. For both U and V the bias remains constant before and after the adjustment methods. However, the spread halves after the NN adjustment

		NEMS4	BC	RNN	S2S
U	$RMSE_S$ [m/s]	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
	$RMSE_U$ [m/s]	4.5	3.6	1.7	1.2
V	$RMSE_S$ [m/s]	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.1
	$RMSE_U$ [m/s]	4.5	3.7	1.6	1.3

Table 4.4: Systematic and unsystematic errors for the wind components, evaluated for all methods.

methods.

The behavior of the systematic error can be deepened by watching the MBE values. These underline the mean over- or underestimation of the values. The values are as follows: NEMS = 2.4 m/s, BC = 1.0 m/s, RNN = -0.3 m/s and S2S = -0.9 m/s. These confirm the hypothesis of overestimation and underestimation, the least bias had by RNN.

Generally, NN models manage to decrease the spread of many quantities and remove the bias with a performance comparable to the BC method. This makes the RNN and S2S methods better than the previous one. The S2S seems to be slightly more accurate than the other.

4.2 Snow data

The NN adjustment methods manage to improve the meteorological data by decreasing both the spread and the bias. Now, the analysis studies what improvements this brings to the snow simulations. As before, the data coming from BC adjustment are kept for direct comparison.

From the figure 4.9, showing the snow height profiles, the improvement in modeling the mass balance is clear. Both the evolution modeled with the NN adjusted data are closer to the measurements. In particular, the S2S has a

Figure 4.9: Snow height evolution simulated with all the datasets.

good simulation of the melting phase, arriving to the complete melting close to the measured data.

Similarly, the snow surface temperature (Fig. 4.10) shows good improvements in the bias error for both the NN methods and small spread for the S2S adjustment.

Figure 4.10: Snow surface temperature scatter plot for the NEMS4 model and all adjustment methods.

At this point a deeper analysis is performed computing the index d_r for all the methods used. The values for every quantity and the mean are given in the table 4.5. Here, the overall improvement is evident for both the NN

d_r	NEMS4	BC	RNN	S2S
HS	-0.88	-0.71	-0.72	-0.56
SWE	-0.91	-0.73	-0.83	-0.70
TSS	0.40	0.39	0.72	0.78
Temp	0.45	0.57	0.64	0.68
LWC	0.07	0.65	0.50	0.65
Density	0.65	0.70	0.66	0.66
Hardness	0.26	0.60	0.64	0.67
gsize	-0.06	0.01	0.15	0.17
gtype	0.52	0.74	0.77	0.79
Mean	0.05	0.25	0.28	0.35

Table 4.5: Values of d_r index for all the snow quantities, modeled using the adjusted data with all the methods.

methods and more pronounced for the S2S. In every single quantity, S2S is the adjustment that works better than the others, except for the density.

To investigate more the errors performed by each method for every quantity, the values of $RMSE$ are shown in figure 4.11. Here, S2S is clearly the method

Figure 4.11: Systematic and unsystematic error for every adjustment method and every quantity (HS: snow height, SWE: snow water equivalent, TSS: snow surface temperature, LWC: liquid water content, gsize: grain size).

that generate the least error overall. Some notable performances are shown by the $RMSE_S$ in TSS and snow height. RNN method has overall good efficiency but lacks in some quantities, such as LWC and HS.

The analysis of the internal quantities of the snowpack can be done also with direct comparison of the output, displayed one by one as follow: grain type in figure 4.12, temperature in figure 4.13, grain size in 4.14, density in figure 4.15 and liquid water content in 4.16. This allow us to check the differences in the model outputs. In the grain type the important features that are modeled in the AWS simulation are the rounded grains around January, the precipitation particles (PP) present during the snowfalls, the two dept hoar (DH) layers and the evolution of melt forms (MF) during the thaw. In the simulation done with NEMS4 data only one of the DH layer is present and all the other features are absent. The RG are not modeled for an overestimation of the temperature

Figure 4.12: The grain type evolution throughout the winter season of the snowpack as simulated using NEMS4 input data and the three correction methods compared to the simulations initialized using measured data, kept as a reference. The grain types are as follows: PP: precipitation particles, DF: decomposing and fragmented particles, RG: rounded grains, FC: faceted crystals, DH: dept hoar, SH: surface hoar, MF: melt forms and MFcr: melt freeze crust. Particular attention should be paid to the hoar layers, as are the most fragile ones, the MF formation.

gradient (Fig. 4.13b) that force the kinetic growth. Similarly the absence of PP is mainly due to the overestimation of the wind. Furthermore, this simulation incorrectly produces a thick melt-freeze crust at the base of the snowpack and a low melting. The simulation using BC adjusted data has the same problems except for the second DH layer and the more correct melting. The two NN simulations are better and similar to each other. Both produce the RG layers in January and have the PP during and after the snowfalls. S2S data show a good melting phase, but lack in the DH layers as only one is simulated. On the other hand, RNN output shows both the DH layers (even if one is particularly thin) but not a good melting.

With respect to temperature, the only relevant differences to be noted are in the vertical gradient. This is determined by the TA and the snow cover structure. It is evident that the simulations from the NEMS4 and BC data have a superficial temperature underestimated and this force a higher gradient in the snowpack. The grain size in the snowpack does not change much, except for the hoar and crusts. In figure 4.14, the discussion is similar to that of one done for the gain type and, in particular, for the DH layers. The density is also more or less constant before melting. The NEMS4 and BC data are more vertically variable than the reference. On the other hand, the NN adjusted data do not model the area on the top of the snowpack where the density is higher around the end of March. This corresponds to a melt-freeze crust (Fig. 4.15) that is not modeled by these simulations. The LWC gives information only about the melting and the results stress the point that NEMS4 and RNN do not perform well.

The particular performance of all methods for the density induces us to deepen the understanding of this quantity. To do so, the evolution of MBE and SDoR during winter is presented in figures 4.17 and 4.18, respectively. The BC method produce the least bias over the whole winter, performing well also during the melting period. The NN models, instead, have a negative bias for the first part of the year. During the melting period the density modeled with these data has a strong overestimation, compared to the one modeled with raw NEMS4 data. On the other hand, the spread seems to be less for the NN methods than for the BC, at least until the thaw. During the melting the NN error increases, whereas the one of BC data oscillates around lower values.

Thus, the only variable in which the NN methods have a worse performance is density, where the melting period plays a fundamental role in decreasing the accuracy of the data. In summary, the method that better produces the meteorological data to run the snowpack simulation is the S2S neural network. The discrepancies in the snowpack structure are limited between the simulation done with S2S adjusted data and the simulation using AWS measurements. This makes the model possibly useful for short term predictions. The reliability of short-term simulation increases compared to these seasonal ones as the starting point could be the snowpack simulated using the AWS measurements.

Temperature

Figure 4.13: The temperature evolution throughout the winter season of the snowpack as simulated using using NEMS4 input data and the three correction methods compared to the simulations initialized using measured data, kept as a reference. The colored scale goes from 0 to -20 °C in all the pictures. The vertical gradient is at last the forcing of different snow methamorphisms, thus it is the main difference to be notetd. AWS is the profile simulated with measured data, NEMS4 with raw NWM output; whereas the BC profile is simulated using bias corrected data, RNN and S2S using the recurrent teural network and sequence to sequence adjustment method, respectively.

Figure 4.14: The grain size evolution throughout the winter season of the snow-pack as simulated using NEMS4 input data and the three correction methods compared to the simulations initialized using measured data, kept as a reference. AWS is the profile simulated with measured data, NEMS4 with raw NWM output; whereas the BC profile is simulated using bias corrected data, RNN and S2S using the recurrent neural network and sequence to sequence adjustment method, respectively.

Figure 4.15: The density evolution throughout the winter season of the snowpack as simulated using using NEMS4 input data and the three correction methods compared to the simulations initialized using measured data, kept as a reference. AWS is the profile simulated with measured data, NEMS4 with raw NWM output; whereas the BC profile is simulated using bias corrected data, RNN and S2S using the recurrent neural network and sequence to sequence adjustment method, respectively.

Figure 4.16: The liquid water content evolution throughout the winter season of the snowpack as simulated using NEMS4 input data and the three correction methods compared to the simulations initialized using measured data, kept as a reference. AWS is the profile simulated with measured data, NEMS4 with raw NWM output; whereas the BC profile is simulated using bias corrected data, RNN and S2S using the recurrent neural network and sequence to sequence adjustment method, respectively.

Figure 4.17: Evolution of the mean bias error for the density. Here BC data oscillate around zero, whereas the NN scaled data have a negative bias for most of the year.

Figure 4.18: Evolution of the standard deviation of residuals for the density. The NN models have the lowest error until the beginning of the melting period.

However, the two quantities that directly depend on the amount of precipitation (HS and SWE) are poorly modeled. The two NN models allow us to calculate the HS for the snowpack. In the following section, the analysis is repeated including the simulations where the HS forcing are used.

4.2.1 Snow height forcing

SNOWPACK allows us to use the measured snow height to force the modeled one, adapting the connected quantities (as density). In the following simulated data, the HS coming from the NN models has been used to force the simulation as that measured. Since the comparison between NN methods, BC adjustment and raw data has been already established, from now on only the data from RNN and S2S are used. The label "_hs" is used for the data obtained with the HS forcing.

The improvements of the snow height modeling can be seen in Figure 4.19. Here, for both the model the HS forcing brings the data closer to the measure-

Figure 4.19: Simulated snow height with and without forcing using the NN adjusted data.

ments for the whole winter.

The snow surface temperature, on the other hand, do not seem to undertake any changes.

All the differences in the simulations are resumed using d_r in table 4.6. On average, the performance improves applying the HS forcing. Nevertheless, strong differences are exhibited among the quantities. HS and SWE improve drastically for both models and also the grain type and size have a slight enhancement. On the other hand, many quantities performance decrease as temperature, LWC, density and hardness; most of the quantities of the internal snowpack.

Figure 4.20: Snow surface temperature using NN adjusted data with and without HS forcing.

d_r	RNN	RNN_hs	S2S	S2S_hs
HS	-0.72	-0.14	-0.56	0.39
SWE	-0.83	-0.45	-0.70	0.02
TSS	0.73	0.73	0.78	0.77
Temp	0.64	0.51	0.68	0.41
LWC	0.50	0.31	0.65	-0.36
Density	0.66	0.72	0.66	0.50
Hardness	0.64	0.71	0.67	0.45
gsiz	0.15	0.56	0.17	0.20
gtype	0.77	0.87	0.79	0.84
Mean	0.28	0.42	0.35	0.36

Table 4.6: Values of d_r for all snow quantities, comparing the results with and without HS forcing.

The grain types of the layers give a good idea of the snowpack structure. This can be seen in figure 4.21 for the simulation using AWS data, the data obtained with the two NN adjustment methods with and without the HS forcing. The main improvement in grain types of the layers is given by the forcing is the simulation of the DH layers. Furthermore, other less important details are simulated when the HS forcing is used.

It is beyond the scope of this work to understand the implications of the forcing using the snow height in the simulation. We can say that the possibility of improving the estimation of HS is concrete and functional but undermines the simulation of other quantities. The use of HS forcing can be limited to applications focused on the availability of water and snow on the ground, where the internal structure of the snowpack is not important. It should be avoided, if the focus is on the layer and their structure, which seem to worsen in results if the forcing is used.

Grain Type

Figure 4.21: The grain type evolution of the snowpack as simulated using measured data (kept as reference), the data adjusted using the two NN methods with and without the HS forcing. The grain types are as follows: PP: precipitation particles, DF: decomposing and fragmented particles, RG: rounded grains, FC: faceted crystals, DH: depth hoar, SH: surface hoar, MF: melt forms and MFcr: melt freeze crust. Particular attention is to be paid to the hoar layers as are the most fragile ones, the MF formation.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

In this work, we try to improve the simulations of the snowpack started with NWMs data. To do this, different NWMs are used, namely ERA5 reanalysis, NEMS4 and NEMS GLOBAL model outputs. Firstly, a validation of these against an AWS data kept as reference is done. Later, the same data are used to start the snowpack simulations. The outputs of these are compared with the simulation started with the AWS measurements using the same method.

The use of different indexes has been applied to resumming complicated information on large datasets. These are not new, but have never been used in the nivological field and together provide complete information about the distributions. The index of agreement d_r showed good versatility and allowed for a direct comparison between different quantities. The combined use of other indexes, such as $RMSE$, allowed us to deepen our knowledge about the deviation of a single quantity or over a determined period. However, the first step using a general and adimensional index makes it possible to focus where needed. This allows us to understand which quantities are more accurate (as RH and ISWR) and which ones are not as good (as TA and winds components). Furthermore, the use of these indexes pointed out that the NEMS4 model is the best in producing data that better simulate the snowpack, compared to AWS measurements.

The comparison of meteorological and nivological data showed an important deviation between the simulated and measured data. Thus, different adjustment methods have been implemented to scale the meteorological data from the NEMS4 model. A data-driven method based on linear regression, called bias correction (BC), is implemented to adjust the NEMS4 output to the AWS data. Increasing the complexity of the methods, two different neural network structures have been constructed, tailored over the adjustment of several meteorological data and the simulation of two nivological quantities: the snow surface temperature and the snow height. The first is the recurrent neural network (RNN) and the second is the sequence-to-sequence network, both suitable to work with time series.

The BC method has good performance in some quantities, such as ISWR

and TA, and is limited in others, such as RH and wind components. This is mainly due to its simple structure that permits correction only in the linear form and not in the spread of the data, nor correction focused on determined values or deviations. The simulations done using these data show an overall limited improvement that produces limited improvements in the simulation of the snowpack.

The newly adapted neural network models show good improvements on the meteorological data. These have great precision in modeling the winds and the temperature that are both key quantities in the modeling of the snowpack. Their ability to model new quantities is useful to fill the data gap between the NWM and the AWS, given by the availability of TSS and HS. In the simulations, the meteorological data coming from the NN models produce good result, close to the simulation done using the AWS measurements. Between the two models, S2S has in numerous occasions better performance than the RNN model. The HS forcing, at last, can be a strong instrument to use the modeled HS by the neural network, but has some downsides to be investigated.

In the end, the S2S adjustment method showed good potentiality in using the NWM data to perform reliable simulations of the snowpack. The big limitation of the methods presented in this work is the requirement of big amount of data and therefore the presence of the AWS in the point to be simulated. This limits the application of this method to short forecast in places where the AWS is already present, using the NWM data. Furthermore can be used to substitute any measurement instrument in already existing AWS, such as surface thermometer.

Snow modeling research is moving toward higher spatiality of the data, leaning on the availability of meteorological data. The main way to do this is to increase the resolution of NWM in the area of interest with elevated computational costs. If the interest is to have data over precise locations, the approach in this work can be useful and easy from a computational point of view. This can be applied mainly to the snow stability evaluation for short time forecast in the AWS point location. Further, the interest of the amount of seasonal snow is growing for managing the water availability. This approach, adapted over longer period and focused only over HS and SWE, could be one way to address this issue.

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